

MDMC

Master in Data Management
and Curation

Master in Data Management and Curation

Metadata Extraction and JSON Export Pipeline
for LAGE Sequencing Data

Supervisors

ORNELLA AFFINITO

VALERIO PIOMPONI

Candidate

Lesly TSOPTIO FOUANG

2025–2026

Finanziato
dall'Unione europea
NextGenerationEU

Ministero
dell'Università
e della Ricerca

Italiadomani
PIANO NAZIONALE
DI RIPRESA E RESILIENZA

This course has been funded by the European Union – NextGenerationEU within the projects:

- *NFFA-DI cod. IR0000015 - Missione 4, “Istruzione e Ricerca” – Componente 2, “Dalla ricerca all’impresa” – Linea di investimento 3.1, “Fondo per la realizzazione di un sistema integrato di infrastrutture di ricerca e innovazione” – Azione 3.1.1, “Creazione di nuove IR o potenziamento di quelle esistenti che concorrono agli obiettivi di Eccellenza Scientifica di Horizon Europe e costituzione di reti” (CUP B53C22004310006)*

[NFFA-DI : Nano Foundries Fine Analysis - Digital Infrastructure](#)

- *EFC cod. SSU2024 – 00002 - Missione 4, “Istruzione e Ricerca” – Componente 1, “Potenziamento dell’offerta dei servizi all’istruzione: dagli asili nido all’ università” – Linea di investimento 3.4, “Didattica e competenze universitarie avanzate” – Sub-Investimento, “Rafforzamento delle scuole universitarie superiori” (CUP G97G24000100007)*

[EFC : Educating Future Citizen](#)

Author's Declaration

I, Lesly TSOPTIO FOUGANG, declare that this thesis entitled, **Metadata Extraction and JSON Export Pipeline for LAGE Sequencing Data** and the work presented therein are my own.

I certify that:

- This work was performed principally during the MDMC internship in the Laboratory of Data Engineering (LADE) at AREA SCIENCE PARK, Trieste.
- If any part of this thesis has previously been submitted for a degree or any other qualification at this University or any other institution, this has been clearly stated.
- Where I have relied on the published work of others, this is always clearly attributed.
- Where the thesis is based on work I have done in collaboration with others, I have made clear exactly what was done by others and what I contributed.
- With respect to AI technologies :
 - I acknowledge the use of [ChatGPT](#) to identify improvements in the writing style.
 - No content generated by AI technologies was presented as my own work.
- Where I have quoted from the work of others, the source is always cited. Except for such quotations, this thesis is entirely my own work.
- I have acknowledged all major sources of help.

Signature: *Lesly Tsoptio Fougang*

Date: 13/05/2026

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to my supervisors, **Ornella Affinito** and **Valerio Pionponi**, for their guidance, constant availability, and warm support throughout this internship. Their expertise and generosity of time made this work possible.

My appreciation also goes to **Margherita Degasperi** and **Roberto Verardo**, members of the LAGE laboratory team, for their time and thoughtful explanations during the laboratory visit.

I would like to thank the administrative staff of SISSA for their dedication and support throughout the administrative process, in particular **Sabrina Moreno**, **Gabriella Peressini**, **Claudia Parme**, **Milla Bottegal**, and **Francesca Gandolfo**.

I am grateful to the coordinator **Mariarita De Luca** and all the lecturers of the Master in Data Management and Curation programme for their teaching and for the intellectual foundations this programme has provided.

I would also like to warmly thank my fellow students for the welcoming atmosphere and the many enriching conversations we shared throughout this year. A special mention goes to **Ruth Nana**, **Valentin Nkana**, **Franky Nando**, **Ali Hussaini Umar**, **Emmanuel Kagarabi** — I truly enjoyed your company.

Finally, to all those who supported me in any way and whose names I may not have mentioned here, please know that your support has not gone unnoticed and is deeply appreciated.

Abstract

Recent advances in sequencing technologies have led to the production of large-scale genomic datasets, significantly accelerating progress in the life sciences. However, this rapid expansion introduces substantial data management challenges, particularly within sequencing facilities such as the Laboratory of Genomics and Epigenomics (LAGE) in Area Science Park (Trieste). The diversity of file formats, the fragmentation of metadata across multiple sources, and the absence of standardised traceability mechanisms hinder efficient data handling and long-term usability.

This work presents the development of a modular and automated Python pipeline for the extraction, normalisation, and FAIR-compliant packaging of sequencing metadata. The system operates on heterogeneous laboratory outputs, using content-based file identification to drive metadata extraction through eleven specialised modules and packaging datasets as RO-Crate 1.2 research objects with machine-actionable metadata serialised in JSON-LD. The registry-based modular architecture enables the flexible integration of new sequencing platforms without modifying the core system. To enhance data traceability, dedicated utility modules reconstruct sample lineage across multiple experimental steps through recursive project-level data aggregation and chronological sample history generation.

The pipeline was evaluated against three real-world datasets generated by major sequencing platforms at LAGE, including the Illumina NovaSeq6000, the Oxford Nanopore PromethION, and the Illumina BeadStudio iScan. The results demonstrate that the system successfully processes heterogeneous datasets, standardises metadata, reconstructs sample provenance across multiple runs, and generates RO-Crate compliant research objects validated against the RO-Crate 1.2 specification.

From an operational perspective, the pipeline automates metadata extraction across the major sequencing platforms at LAGE, reducing human intervention to output verification and directly addressing the scalability and reproducibility challenges identified at the facility. Beyond this specific context, its domain-agnostic design makes it applicable to any data-intensive facility producing heterogeneous instrument outputs.

Contents

1	Sequencing Data: Background and Challenges	3
1.1	Scientific and Technical Background	3
1.1.1	Fundamentals of Genetic Information	3
1.1.2	Evolution of Sequencing Technologies	3
1.1.3	Types of Sequencing Analyses	4
1.1.4	Sequencing Data and File Formats	4
1.2	Metadata in Sequencing	6
1.2.1	Types of Sequencing Metadata	6
1.2.2	Sample Sheets as Primary Metadata Documents	7
1.3	Case Study: LAGE Sequencing Ecosystem	8
1.3.1	Overview of LAGE	8
1.3.2	Sequencing Platforms	8
1.3.3	Data Production and Storage	10
1.3.4	Data Management Challenges at LAGE	11
1.4	Conceptual Solution Framework	12
1.4.1	FAIR Data Principles	12
1.4.2	RO-Crate as a Practical FAIR Implementation	14
1.5	Overview of the Proposed Pipeline	21
2	Materials, Methods and Pipeline Design	23
2.1	Case Study Datasets	23
2.1.1	ORID0087 – IlluminaNovaSeq6000	23
2.1.2	ORID0085 – Oxford Nanopore PromethION	26
2.1.3	ORID0036 – BeadStudio Illumina iScan	29
2.2	Pipeline Architecture and Implementation	30

2.2.1	The Four-Step Processing Workflow	30
2.2.2	Modular Architecture: Specialized Extraction and Management	31
2.2.3	Performance Benchmarking Module	46
2.2.4	The JSON Metadata Schema	47
2.2.5	Implementation and availability details	50
3	Results and Discussion	52
3.1	Case Study 1: ORID0087 — Illumina NovaSeq6000	52
3.1.1	Files Detected and Extractors Invoked	52
3.1.2	Representative JSON Outputs	53
3.1.3	Sample History Reconstruction	54
3.1.4	RO-Crate Generation	55
3.2	Case Study 2: ORID0085 — Oxford Nanopore PromethION	57
3.2.1	Files Detected and Extractors Invoked	57
3.2.2	Representative JSON Output	58
3.2.3	RO-Crate Generation	59
3.3	Case Study 3: ORID0036 — BeadStudio iScan	60
3.3.1	Files Detected and Extractor Invoked	61
3.3.2	Representative JSON Output	61
3.3.3	RO-Crate Generation	62
3.4	Cross-Dataset Analysis	66
3.4.1	Pipeline Performance Summary	66
3.4.2	Impact on LAGE Data Management Workflow	66
3.4.3	FAIR Compliance Assessment	67
3.5	Limitations	69
3.6	Future Perspectives	70
	General Conclusion	72

A Operational User Guide	73
A.1 Installation	73
A.2 Execution Requirements	74
A.3 Command-Line Usage	74
A.4 Expected Input Structure	76
A.5 Expected Output Structure	77
A.6 Troubleshooting	77
A.7 Version Control Strategy	78
A.8 Guidelines for Adding New Extractors	79
A.9 Summary of Extensibility Mechanism	82
References	84

General Introduction

Sequencing is the process of determining the exact order of building blocks in genetic material. In DNA, these building blocks are four chemical units (A, T, C, and G) that encode the instructions governing how living organisms grow, function, and respond to their environment [1]. By reading this sequence, scientists can identify the genetic basis of diseases, study gene regulation, and develop targeted therapeutic strategies. Sequencing can also be applied to RNA, providing a snapshot of which genes are actively expressed in a cell at a given time.

Historically, sequencing was a slow and labour-intensive process. Early approaches such as Sanger sequencing [2] were limited to short DNA fragments and required substantial manual intervention. The advent of next-generation sequencing (NGS) [3] radically changed this landscape. Modern platforms such as Illumina NovaSeq and Oxford Nanopore Technologies can process millions to billions of DNA fragments in parallel, enabling whole-genome sequencing, RNA sequencing, epigenetic analysis, and large-scale genotyping at a fraction of the time and cost of earlier methods [1].

However, this technological progress comes with a significant trade-off: an unprecedented increase in data generation. Sequencing platforms now routinely produce terabytes of data per run [4]. While this creates new opportunities for discovery, it introduces major challenges in data storage, organisation, and long-term management that are particularly acute in high-throughput sequencing environments.

These challenges are directly evident at the Laboratory of Genomics and Epigenomics (LAGE), hosted by Area Science Park in Trieste. Equipped with many sequencing platforms including the Illumina NovaSeq 6000 and the Oxford Nanopore PromethION 24, LAGE generates approximately 100 TB of raw sequencing data per year, accumulating to nearly 1 petabyte over the ten-year raw data retention period mandated by Italian regulatory requirements. At this scale, manual data management is not only inefficient but unsustainable.

The challenge is compounded by the heterogeneity of sequencing outputs. Data are stored across a variety of file formats including `.fastq.gz`, `.bam`, `.pod5`, and `.csv`, each serving different purposes. A particularly critical but underappreciated dimension of this problem lies in *metadata*: the structured information describing what was sequenced, how, when, and under which conditions. At LAGE, metadata is distributed across sample sheets, quality control exports, instrument configuration files, and run reports, each using platform-specific formats and naming conventions. Inconsistencies such as varying date formats, missing fields, and non-standardised identifiers are common, making it difficult to query, integrate, or reuse metadata across experiments.

This fragmentation has direct consequences for scientific reproducibility. Without a unified metadata representation, reconstructing the provenance of a dataset becomes a manual, error-prone process. This situation directly conflicts with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), which have become the standard for research data management and are increasingly required by funding agencies and public repositories [5].

To address these challenges, this project develops an automated, modular Python pipeline for sequencing metadata extraction, standardisation, and FAIR-compliant packaging. The main contributions of this work are:

- A systematic analysis of the metadata landscape at LAGE, covering three major sequencing platforms (Illumina NovaSeq6000, Oxford Nanopore PromethION, and Illumina iScan) together with their associated quality control instruments;
- Eleven specialised extractor modules capable of processing heterogeneous instrument-native files through content-based detection, without relying on filename conventions;
- A JSON metadata output schema defining a common top-level structure across all extractor modules, and a sample history reconstruction mechanism enabling cross-file sample provenance tracing across multiple sequencing targets and experimental steps;
- Automated RO-Crate packaging producing self-describing, portable research objects compliant with the RO-Crate 1.2 specification [6], validated using the RO-Crate Playground and aligned with the DECOS Common Data Model for institutional deposit.

The pipeline architecture is extensible by design: supporting new sequencing platforms requires only the addition of a new extractor module, without modifying the core system. The complete source code is publicly available at https://github.com/RitAreaSciencePark/LAGE_Metadata_Extraction.

This manuscript is organised into three chapters.

Chapter 1 presents the scientific and technical background, including sequencing technologies, the FAIR data principles, and the RO-Crate framework.

Chapter 2 describes the materials and methods, detailing the case study datasets, pipeline architecture, and packaging strategy.

Chapter 3 presents the results, evaluating the pipeline across three real-world datasets and assessing its impact on data management workflows at LAGE. The manuscript concludes with a general conclusion summarising the main findings and outlining future directions, including integration with the web app DECOS and real-time metadata capture.

Chapter 1

Sequencing Data: Background and Challenges

Chapter Overview

This chapter establishes the scientific and technical foundations of this work. It begins with an introduction to high-throughput sequencing technologies, the types of analyses they support, and the data formats they generate. It then examines the role of metadata in sequencing experiments and the challenges posed by its heterogeneity and lack of standardisation, illustrated through the concrete case of LAGE. The chapter concludes by introducing the conceptual framework adopted to address these challenges: the FAIR data principles and the RO-Crate standard, which together motivate the automated pipeline developed in this work.

1.1 Scientific and Technical Background

1.1.1 Fundamentals of Genetic Information

Genetic information is stored in deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA), composed of four nucleotide bases: adenine (A), thymine (T), cytosine (C), and guanine (G), whose sequence encodes the instructions for cellular function, growth, and reproduction [1]. Ribonucleic acid (RNA) acts as an intermediary between DNA and proteins, reflecting which genes are actively expressed at a given time. Sequencing both molecules enables the identification of genetic variants, the study of gene regulation, and the development of targeted therapeutic strategies.

1.1.2 Evolution of Sequencing Technologies

DNA sequencing technologies have evolved through three generations, each offering distinct capabilities.

First-Generation Sequencing

Sanger sequencing, introduced in the 1970s [2], relies on chain-terminating nucleotides to determine sequences with high accuracy. Despite its reliability, it is limited in throughput and requires substantial manual intervention. The Human Genome Project, completed after 13 years at an estimated cost of \$2.7 billion, exemplifies these constraints [7].

Next-Generation Sequencing

Next-generation sequencing (NGS) platforms enable massively parallel sequencing, processing millions to billions of fragments simultaneously [3]. This reduces human genome sequencing to approximately 7–10 days and significantly lowers per-base cost [8]. Illumina sequencing, one of the most widely adopted NGS technologies, produces highly accurate short reads suitable for whole-genome sequencing, RNA-seq, and amplicon-based studies. However, reliance on PCR amplification can introduce biases in repetitive genomic regions.

Third-Generation Sequencing

Third-generation platforms such as Oxford Nanopore Technologies enable direct sequencing of long DNA or RNA molecules without prior amplification, producing reads spanning several kilobases to megabase scale [1]. This improves resolution of structural variants, enables real-time data acquisition, and allows direct detection of epigenetic modifications such as DNA methylation without additional chemical treatment [9]. A human genome can now be sequenced in approximately one to two days [8], though higher raw error rates remain a limitation mitigated by improved basecalling algorithms and increased coverage.

1.1.3 Types of Sequencing Analyses

High-throughput sequencing supports four main analytical categories.

DNA sequencing determines complete or partial genomic sequences through whole-genome sequencing (WGS) or targeted approaches such as whole exome sequencing (WES), enabling identification of variants, insertions, deletions, and structural rearrangements.

RNA sequencing (RNA-seq) measures gene expression by quantifying RNA abundance, revealing active genes, alternative splicing events, and transcript isoforms.

Epigenetic analyses investigate chemical modifications such as DNA methylation that regulate gene activity without altering the sequence.

Genotyping identifies single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) across individuals or populations, supporting studies of genetic diversity and disease susceptibility.

1.1.4 Sequencing Data and File Formats

Sequencing data can be classified into three main categories: primary data, secondary data, and auxiliary data. The following subsections provide a brief description of each category.

a. Primary Data: The “Raw” Physical Signal

Raw data corresponds to the direct output generated by the sensors of a sequencing instrument. It is typically stored in proprietary binary formats that are not directly readable by humans or standard bioinformatics tools without dedicated preprocessing and conversion pipelines. The exact format of the raw output depends on the sequencing technology used:

- **Illumina:** produces binary **Base Call (BCL)** files, which contain base calls and associated quality scores derived from raw fluorescence intensity signals generated during the sequencing run.
- **Oxford Nanopore Technologies:** records the raw ionic current signal (measured in picoamperes) produced as DNA or RNA molecules pass through a nanopore. That raw signal is stored in **POD5** progressively replacing the older FAST5 format in current workflows.
- **Illumina iScan:** produces **IDAT** (Intensity Data) files containing the raw fluorescence intensity values measured at each probe location on the BeadChip array. These files serve as the primary input for downstream genotyping and DNA methylation analysis tools such as minfi or GenomeStudio.

b. Secondary Data: The “Digital” Sequence

Secondary data is the result of applying a computational algorithm, such as a *Basecaller*, to the primary data. This process translates physical signals into a biological sequence of nucleotides (A, T, C, and G). After base-calling and demultiplexing, the data is transformed into standard bioinformatic formats:

- **FASTQ files:** store nucleotide sequences with per-base Phred quality scores **Phred quality score**¹.
- **SAM/BAM files:** store read alignments to a reference genome.

c. Auxiliary Metadata and Provenance

Beyond sequence data, an experiment produces critical auxiliary files that are essential for the **FAIRification** of the dataset:

- **Sample Sheets (CSV):** Provide the mapping required for demultiplexing, linking specific barcodes and indexes to sample identifiers.

¹score representing the probability that a base call is incorrect

- **Configuration and Log Files:** Document instrument parameters, software versions, and flow cell chemistry. In a data curation context, these are crucial for establishing **data provenance**, often modeled using standards like *PROV-O* or packaged within *RO-Crate* structures.

Together, these different data types highlight the multi-layered nature of sequencing data, ranging from raw signal acquisition to processed analytical outputs, and underscore the importance of proper data management and standardization.

1.2 Metadata in Sequencing

Metadata refers to structured information that describes data and provides context for its interpretation. In sequencing experiments, it encompasses all information necessary to understand how a sample was collected, prepared, sequenced, and processed — from organism identity to basecalling software version. Well-structured metadata are essential for reproducibility, traceability, and data reuse. Without them, sequencing data lose much of their scientific value, and reconstructing the history of a sample sequenced across multiple runs or platforms becomes intractable.

1.2.1 Types of Sequencing Metadata

Sequencing metadata exists at several distinct levels, each describing a different dimension of the experimental process [10]:

- **Sample metadata** describes the biological origin of the material being sequenced. It includes the organism or species, tissue type, sample collection date, preservation method, and any experimental condition or treatment applied to the sample prior to sequencing. This layer anchors the data to its biological context and is indispensable for any downstream comparative or integrative analysis.
- **Library metadata** describes the biochemical transformation applied to the biological material before it can be sequenced. It includes the library preparation protocol, the fragmentation method, the adapter sequences ligated to the DNA fragments, the index or barcode sequences used to distinguish samples in multiplexed runs, and the demultiplexing parameters applied after sequencing. Library metadata is critical for interpreting read quality and for troubleshooting sequencing failures.
- **Run and instrument metadata** describes the technical conditions under which the sequencing reaction was carried out. It includes the sequencing platform and instrument model, the instrument serial number, the run date and identifier, the sequencing chemistry version, and the base-calling software and its version. This layer provides the technical provenance of the raw data and is essential for assessing platform-specific biases and for replicating results.

- **Quality control metadata** describes the outcome of quality assessment steps performed before sequencing (concentration, purity ratios, fragment size distributions from NanoDrop or TapeStation) and after sequencing (Phred scores, duplication rates, GC content, assessed using FastQC[11]).

Each of these metadata layers is produced by different instruments, software tools, and laboratory personnel at different stages of the experimental workflow. This distributed production is precisely what makes sequencing metadata inherently heterogeneous and difficult to consolidate without dedicated tooling; a challenge that directly motivates the modular architecture of the pipeline described in [Chapter 2](#).

1.2.2 Sample Sheets as Primary Metadata Documents

Among all metadata documents produced in a sequencing workflow, the *sample sheet* occupies a central role. It is a structured file that serves simultaneously as a configuration input for the sequencing instrument and as the primary metadata record for the resulting dataset, encoding both technical run parameters and sample identities.

In **Illumina** sequencing, the sample sheet is a multi-section CSV structured around named blocks: `[Header]` (investigator name, experiment name, run date), `[Manifests]` (array design identifier), and `[Data]` (one row per sample with identifiers, well position, pool ID, and Sentrix barcode).

In **Oxford Nanopore** sequencing, the run metadata is stored as plain-text summary reports, Markdown run reports or a JSON configuration file encoding key fields such as `product_name` (instrument model, e.g., PromethION24), `flow_cell_id` (flow cell identifier), `sequencing_kit` (library kit version), `basecalling_model` (basecalling algorithm and chemistry), `run_date` (ISO 8601 format), and `sample_id` (sample identifier).

The contrast between these formats illustrates concretely why metadata standardisation is non-trivial. Illumina uses a section-delimited CSV with implicit field semantics while Nanopore uses a flat JSON with explicit key names. For instance, the same concept is encoded as `Sample_ID` in one platform and `sample_id` in the other, and run dates appear in a named header block in one case and a flat JSON field in the other. These differences make a single generic parser impossible and directly motivate the multi-module architecture described in [Chapter 2](#).

Metadata Standardisation Problem

In practice, sequencing metadata are often heterogeneous and poorly standardised. Differences in formats, naming conventions, and field completeness complicate data integration and limit automation. Within a single laboratory, metadata quality degrades over time as personnel change and naming conventions drift. Without harmonised metadata, it is not possible to reliably trace a sample's history across runs, reconstruct data lineage, or deposit data in

repositories requiring machine-readable metadata. Although community standards have been proposed to address this problem, their adoption in routine laboratory practice has remained limited. This gap between available standards and actual practice is precisely the problem this project addresses, and it is examined in [section 1.4](#).

1.3 Case Study: LAGE Sequencing Ecosystem

1.3.1 Overview of LAGE

The Laboratory of Genomics and Epigenomics (LAGE), hosted by Area Science Park in Trieste, Italy, is a national facility dedicated to genomics and epigenomics research [12]. Operating under an open-access model, LAGE provides comprehensive DNA and RNA analysis services across human, animal, and microbial samples. Its sequencing portfolio includes Whole Genome Sequencing, RNA-sequencing, exome sequencing, targeted panels, microbiome profiling (16S/ITS), and high-throughput genotyping through Illumina Infinium arrays. The facility spans approximately 220 m² with 20 workstations and operates a dual service model integrating academic collaborations with industrial R&D projects.

1.3.2 Sequencing Platforms

Three instruments generate the datasets used in this project, each with distinct output formats and processing requirements.

ILLUMINA NOVASeq 6000

The Illumina NovaSeq 6000 ([Figure 1.1](#)) is a high-throughput NGS platform based on sequencing-by-synthesis (SBS) technology, producing billions of short reads per run through fluorescent nucleotide incorporation and optical imaging [13]. It supports WGS, RNA-seq, and amplicon-based studies including 16S rRNA and ITS sequencing. Runs last 13–44 hours depending on flow cell type, and are managed through the **NovaSeq Control Software** [14]. Raw output consists of **BCL files**, which must be demultiplexed and converted to FASTQ using tools such as *bcl2fastq* [15, 16].

Figure 1.1 *Illumina NovaSeq 6000 [13].*

Oxford Nanopore PromethION 24

The PromethION 24 (Figure 1.2), developed by Oxford Nanopore Technologies, measures changes in ionic current as nucleic acid molecules translocate through nanoscale protein pores, enabling direct long-read sequencing without amplification [17]. It supports up to 24 simultaneous flow cells (FLO-PRO114M, R10.4.1 chemistry) and generates up to 200 Gb of raw data per flow cell over a typical 72-hour run. The system is operated through **MinKNOW** software with real-time GPU-accelerated basecalling. Raw signals are stored in **POD5** format and converted to FASTQ or BAM by the **Dorado** basecaller. The platform additionally supports direct detection of base modifications such as DNA methylation [17].

Figure 1.2 *Oxford Nanopore PromethION 24 [18].*

Illumina iScan Scanning System

The Illumina iScan (Figure 1.3) is a high-resolution microarray scanner used for genotyping and DNA methylation analysis through fluorescence-based detection of BeadChip arrays [19]. Laser excitation measures fluorescence intensity at each probe location; intensity values are

then used to infer allele presence or methylation levels. Scanning is managed through the **iScan Control Software** and requires a **DMA P** file defining chip layout and probe positions for each BeadChip. Primary outputs are **IDAT files** containing raw fluorescence intensity values, accompanied by XML metadata and raw scan images.

Figure 1.3 *Illumina iScan microarray scanning system [20].*

1.3.3 Data Production and Storage

Data Volume

Sequencing activities at LAGE generate substantial volumes of data on a yearly basis. The amount of data produced varies depending on the sequencing platform:

- **Illumina platforms:** Each sequencing run generates approximately **0.5 TB** of data. With an estimated **80–100 runs per year**, this corresponds to a total annual volume of approximately **40–50 TB**.
- **Oxford Nanopore platforms:** Each run produces significantly larger datasets, averaging up to **2 TB per run**. With around **20 runs per year**, this results in an estimated annual volume of up to **50 TB**.

Overall, the total data production at LAGE is estimated at approximately **100 TB per year**, corresponding to a cumulative storage requirement of nearly **1000 TB over a ten-year retention period for raw data**.

Data Storage and Archiving

All sequencing data are stored within the **ORFEO Data Center File System**, which provides the computational and storage infrastructure for managing large-scale genomic datasets. A standardized data retention policy is applied:

- **Raw data:** retained for up to **10 years**, in compliance with Italian regulatory requirements.
- **Processed data and metadata:** retained for approximately **1 year**.

Any deviation from these policies must be formally agreed upon with the client and remain compliant with applicable legal and institutional regulations.

Implications for Data Management

The combination of high data volume, heterogeneous file formats, and long-term storage requirements introduces significant challenges for data organization and accessibility.

1.3.4 Data Management Challenges at LAGE

The observations below are grounded in a systematic audit of LAGE's data infrastructure and metadata workflows conducted during the first phase of this internship, complemented by direct consultation with laboratory staff.

Unsustainable Manual Curation

Manual curation of sequencing metadata is impractical at the scale of LAGE's operations. With approximately 120 runs per year across Illumina and Nanopore platforms, opening each sample sheet, identifying and extracting relevant fields, checking for consistency, and recording results manually represents a significant and unsustainable operational overhead. Beyond the time cost, manual curation degrades in quality at scale: inconsistent field naming, missing values, and operator-specific conventions accumulate with each run, compounding the very challenges they fail to address.

Absence of Structured Sample Tracking and Data Lineage

There is no standardised mechanism to link multiple runs of the same sample across instruments and time points. A sample sequenced first on the NovaSeq6000 and subsequently on the PromethION exists as isolated records in platform-specific files sharing no common schema. Answering the fundamental question *"what runs has this sample been through, and what were the outcomes?"* currently requires manual cross-referencing across directories, hindering longitudinal analyses and external data sharing.

Reproducibility and Long-Term Data Interpretability at Risk

In a laboratory where personnel change over time, sequencing runs span multiple platforms, and raw data must be retained for ten years, an undocumented dataset can become uninterpretable within its own retention period. A sequencing file with an ambiguous sample identifier or a missing library kit field cannot be reliably reanalysed, integrated with data from a different platform, or integrated in a digital ecosystem such as DECOS² (<https://github.com/RitAreaSciencePark/decos>) requiring structured metadata. Therefore, the reproducibility deficit at LAGE grows with every run whose metadata is recorded inconsistently or incompletely.

²DECOS is a FAIR-compliant institutional digital ecosystem hosted at the ORFEO Data Center, Trieste, for standardised metadata management across Area Science Park life sciences facilities.

Summary: A Diagnostic Through the FAIR Lens

Viewed through the FAIR data principles introduced in [section 1.4](#), the challenges described above correspond to specific, identifiable violations, summarised in [Table 1.1](#).

Table 1.1 *Mapping of LAGE data management challenges to specific FAIR principle violations.*

Challenge	FAIR Violation	Consequence
Heterogeneous file formats, no shared schema	I1, R1.3	Cannot integrate data across platforms or deposit in repositories.
No sample tracking or data lineage	I3, R1.2	Cannot reconstruct provenance or link related datasets.
Undescribed or inconsistently described data	F2, R1	Data becomes uninterpretable; reproducibility compromised.
No automation; manual curation at scale	F4, R1.3	Metadata quality degrades with throughput; not indexable.

Row colour indicates FAIR category: Interoperable/Reusable Findable/Reusable

These observations collectively motivate the development of an automated, modular pipeline that operates on existing instrument-native files, extracts and normalises their metadata automatically, and packages the result in a machine-readable, FAIR-compliant format. The conceptual foundations of this approach are introduced in the following section.

1.4 Conceptual Solution Framework

The challenges at LAGE reflect a systemic problem in research data management at scale, one the scientific community has addressed through shared principles and practical standards. This section introduces the two conceptual pillars underpinning the solution developed here: the FAIR data principles and the RO-Crate standard.

1.4.1 FAIR Data Principles

The FAIR data principles were formally introduced in 2016 by Wilkinson et al. in *Scientific Data* [5] and have since been adopted by the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), Horizon Europe funding programmes, and a growing number of institutional repositories [21]. **FAIR** stands for **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable, and **R**eusable. A critical aspect of the FAIR principles that is frequently misunderstood is their emphasis on *machine-actionability*,

which is the ability of computational systems to find, access, interpret, and integrate data with minimal human intervention. FAIR is not primarily about making data readable by humans; it is about making data processable by machines. This distinction is essential in the context of high-throughput sequencing, where the volume of data makes any purely manual approach to data discovery and integration unscalable. The specific requirements for each pillar are detailed below.

The Four Pillars of FAIR

Findable: The first step in data reuse is the ability to locate it. To be findable, data and metadata must be assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers and described with rich metadata that enables their discovery through automated search systems.

- **F1.** (Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier (PID).
- **F2.** Data are described with rich metadata.
- **F3.** Metadata clearly include the identifier of the data they describe.
- **F4.** (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource.

Accessible: Once found, users and machines must know how the data can be accessed, including under what conditions and through what protocol.

- **A1.** (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised, open protocol.
- **A1.1.** The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable.
- **A1.2.** The protocol allows for authentication and authorisation where necessary.
- **A2.** Metadata remain accessible even when the data are no longer available.

Interoperable: Data must be capable of being integrated with other datasets, which requires the use of standardised formats, shared languages, and controlled vocabularies that are understood across different systems and platforms.

- **I1.** (Meta)data use a formal, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
- **I2.** (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles.
- **I3.** (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data.

Reusable: The ultimate goal of FAIR is to optimise the reuse of data through robust documentation, explicit provenance, and legal clarity.

- **R1.** (Meta)data are richly described with accurate and relevant attributes.
- **R1.1.** (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage licence.
- **R1.2.** (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance.
- **R1.3.** (Meta)data comply with domain-relevant community standards.

Existing Standards and the Choice of RO-Crate

Several community standards have been proposed to operationalise the FAIR principles in the context of sequencing data. The **Minimum Information about a high-throughput**

SEQuencing Experiment (MINSEQE) standard defines a minimum set of metadata fields required for a sequencing experiment to be interpretable and reproducible [10]. The **MIMARKS** standard extends this framework to marker gene sequencing and environmental samples [22]. The **ISA-Tab** framework provides a general-purpose tabular format for describing multi-omics experiments, structuring metadata across three interconnected levels: Investigation, Study, and Assay [23]. These standards define *what* metadata should be recorded; they do not prescribe how data and metadata should be packaged and made portable.

RO-Crate addresses this complementary concern. Rather than replacing the above standards, it provides a lightweight, format-agnostic packaging layer that can wrap any metadata content, including content structured according to MINSEQE or ISA-Tab, into a self-describing, machine-readable research object. RO-Crate was selected for this work for three concrete reasons directly tied to the operational context of LAGE. First, it imposes no constraints on the format or content of the data files it describes, meaning it can be applied directly to the heterogeneous instrument-native outputs of LAGE without any modification to existing data production workflows. Second, it is natively serialised in JSON-LD, a format that is both human-readable and machine-interpretable, and that uses the Schema.org vocabulary to provide unambiguous semantic descriptions of entities such as files, instruments, organisations, and software tools. Third, it is supported by an actively maintained Python library, `rocrate-py`, which provides a programmatic API for constructing and writing compliant crates, directly enabling the automated pipeline architecture developed in this work [6].

1.4.2 RO-Crate as a Practical FAIR Implementation

Concept and Foundations

RO-Crate (Research Object Crate) is a community-developed standard for packaging research data with its associated metadata in a structured, machine-readable, and portable format [6]. Developed under the Research Object initiative and now maintained by a broad international consortium, it operationalises the notion of a *Research Object*: a coherent, self-describing unit bundling data, metadata, provenance, and context into a single portable artefact. At its core, an RO-Crate consists of a **root directory** containing data files and a **central metadata descriptor** (`ro-crate-metadata.json`) describing their contents, provenance, and relationships. This minimal structure makes it immediately applicable to heterogeneous datasets without modifying existing workflows.

JSON-LD as the Metadata Representation Format

The metadata file is serialised in **JSON-LD 1.2** [24], the W3C standard for Linked Data serialisation. As a syntactic extension of JSON, JSON-LD adds semantic meaning by linking field names and values to shared vocabularies through a `@context` declaration, offering two advantages: the file remains readable as standard JSON by any text editor, while also being parseable as a linked data graph enabling automated reasoning and integration. A detailed description of the `ro-crate-metadata.json` structure is provided in [subsubsection 1.4.2](#).

Schema.org as the Core Vocabulary

RO-Crate relies on **Schema.org** [25], a vocabulary providing over 800 types and 1,400 properties maintained by Google, Microsoft, Yahoo, and Yandex. Entities in the LAGE RO-Crate are typed using classes such as **Dataset**, **File**, **Organization**, and **SoftwareApplication**, while relationships use properties such as **hasPart**, **creator**, and **instrument**. Because these terms are globally defined, any Schema.org-aware system can interpret the metadata without prior knowledge of the dataset, directly addressing FAIR principles **I1** and enables the **F4** discoverability requirement.

Linked Data Model and Entity Identification

RO-Crate is grounded in the four **Linked Data principles** originally formulated by Tim Berners-Lee: use URIs as names for things; use HTTP URIs so those names can be looked up; provide useful information using the standards (RDF, SPARQL) when a URI is looked up; and include links to other URIs to enable discovery of related things [26]. In practice, each entity in the RO-Crate metadata file is assigned a unique `@id`, typically expressed as an IRI (Internationalised Resource Identifier). For files within the crate, the `@id` is the relative path of the file; for contextual entities such as instruments or organisations, it is either an absolute URI (e.g., an ORCID for a researcher or a URL for an institution) or a local identifier prefixed with `#`. This identification scheme enables three capabilities that are directly relevant to the LAGE use case:

- **Explicit cross-referencing:** a file entity can reference the instrument that generated it, the software that processed it, and the researcher who initiated the run, all through typed `@id` links.
- **Integration with external resources:** a sample entity can be linked to an external database record (e.g., a BioSample accession), enabling traceability beyond the crate.
- **Global interoperability:** because identifiers are IRIs, they are unambiguous across systems and institutions, satisfying FAIR principle **F1**.

Data Entities and Contextual Entities

A fundamental structural feature of the RO-Crate model is the distinction between two categories of entities, each serving a different descriptive function:

- **Data entities** representing the concrete files and directories contained within the crate. They include sequencing output files, sample sheets, QC reports, images, and any other research artefact. Each data entity is identified by the relative path of the corresponding file and is described with metadata such as its name, encoding format, size, creation date, and provenance. Data entities may also reference external resources via persistent identifiers when the underlying file is stored remotely or subject to access restrictions.

The RO-Crate Metadata File Structure

The central descriptor file, `ro-crate-metadata.json`, encodes the entire graph of entities and relationships as a flat JSON-LD array under the `@graph` key. Despite the potentially complex relationships it represents, the flat serialisation keeps the file human-readable and avoids deeply nested structures that would complicate parsing. The file is organised around the following components:

- **Metadata file descriptor:** The first entry in the `@graph` array is a self-description of the metadata file. It declares four things:
 - `@id` set to `ro-crate-metadata.json` identifying the file itself;
 - `@type` set to `CreativeWork`, typing it as a Schema.org creative work;
 - `about` property pointing to `./`, which links this descriptor to the root dataset entity and establishes the entry point for interpreting the entire crate;
 - `conformsTo` property, which explicitly declares compliance with version 1.2 of the RO-Crate specification.

The `@context` field at the top of the file (<https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.2/context>) declares the RO-Crate JSON-LD context, which binds every property used in the file to a globally unambiguous term from the RO-Crate and Schema.org vocabularies. Without this declaration, the `@graph` would be plain JSON with no shared semantic meaning and no guaranteed interoperability across systems. Figure 1.4 shows this descriptor as it appears in a LAGE-generated crate.

```
{
  "@context": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.2/context",
  "@graph": [
    {
      "@id": "ro-crate-metadata.json",
      "@type": "CreativeWork",
      "about": {
        "@id": "./"
      },
      "conformsTo": {
        "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.2"
      }
    }
  ]
}
```

Figure 1.4 Metadata file descriptor of a LAGE RO-Crate (version 1.2).

- **Root data entity:** Represents the overall dataset as a `Dataset` typed entity with `@id` set to `./`. It aggregates all top-level files and subdirectories through the `hasPart` property and carries high-level descriptive metadata including name, description, licence, and publication date. Figure 1.5 shows the root entity of a LAGE crate, where the `description` field encodes an HTML summary of the instruments and file types present in the dataset.


```
{
  "@id": "./",
  "name": "LAGE Experimental Dataset for the Repository: 20250929_ORID0085C",
  "@type": "Dataset",
  "datePublished": "2026-03-27",
  "description": "<p>This dataset contains <b>33</b> files generated through:</p><ul><li><b>Sequencing phase</b></li></ul>",
  "license": "https://opensource.org/licenses/MIT",
  "hasPart": {
    "@id": "20250929_ORID0085C/"
  },
  "humanReadableSize": "2.81 MB"
},
```

Figure 1.5 Root data entity of a LAGE RO-Crate, aggregating all dataset components and carrying high-level descriptive metadata auto-generated by the pipeline.

- **Flat list of data entities:** All files and directories within the dataset are enumerated as a flat list of @id references under the hasPart property of the root dataset entity. Each entry is a JSON object containing a single @id field expressing the relative path of the corresponding file or directory within the crate root. As visible in Figure 1.6, this list mixes two types of references: **file references**, identified by their filename and extension (e.g., 2025-03-13_ext_lupo_05x_sampleTable.csv), and **directory references**, identified by a trailing slash (e.g., LIS14-11-24/). The @graph maintains a flat list of uniquely identified entities that can be individually described, cross-referenced, and retrieved. Each @id listed here corresponds to a fully described entity elsewhere in the @graph, where its metadata (name, format, size...) is recorded in detail.

```
"hasPart": [
  {
    "@id": "2025-03-13_ext_lupo_05x_sampleTable.csv"
  },
  {
    "@id": "2025-03-13_ext_lupo_05x_compactPeakTable.csv"
  },
  {
    "@id": "2025-03-13_ext_lupo_05x.pdf"
  },
  {
    "@id": "LIS14-11-24/"
  },
  {
    "@id": "Pich31-12-24/"
  }
],
```

Figure 1.6 Flat list of hasPart references in a LAGE RO-Crate, enumerating both file entities (identified by filename and extension, e.g., .csv) and directory entities (identified by a trailing slash, e.g., LIS14-11-24/).

- **File data entities:** Each individual file within the crate is described as a fully typed entity in the @graph, identified by its relative path as @id and typed as File using the Schema.org vocabulary. As visible in Figure 1.7, a file entity in a LAGE RO-Crate carries the following fields: name and humanReadableSize for basic identification; description providing an HTML-encoded summary of the file's content and instrument origin; encodingFormat referencing a contextual format entity (#csv-format);

creator linking to the producing organisation (`#lage`); `actionProcess` linking to the sequencing activity that generated the biological data (`#novaseq-sequencing-activity`); and `wasGeneratedBy` linking to the software tool that registered the entity in the crate (`#Crate_Generator`). The combination of `actionProcess` and `wasGeneratedBy` captures two distinct levels of provenance (scientific and technical) in the same entity, jointly satisfying FAIR sub-principles **R1.2** and **I3**.

```
{
  "@id": "20260129_ORID0087_C_ALL_INDEXES.csv",
  "@type": "File",
  "actionProcess": {
    "@id": "#novaseq-sequencing-activity"
  },
  "creator": {
    "@id": "#lage"
  },
  "description": "<i>Instrument report or sample manifest associated with the Illumina NovaSeq6000 run.</i>",
  "encodingFormat": {
    "@id": "#csv-format"
  },
  "humanReadableSize": "14.57 KB",
  "name": "20260129_ORID0087_C_ALL_INDEXES.csv",
  "wasGeneratedBy": {
    "@id": "#Crate_Generator"
  }
},
```

Figure 1.7 A file data entity in a LAGE RO-Crate (`20260129_ORID0087_C_ALL_INDEXES.csv`), showing its encoding format, size, creator, sequencing activity (`actionProcess`), and generating software (`wasGeneratedBy`).

- **Contextual entities:** Organisations, software tools, instruments, and activities are described as contextual entities within the same `@graph`, typed using Schema.org vocabulary and identified by a unique `@id`. As shown in [Figure 1.8](#), the LAGE crate defines two representative contextual entities: the **organisation entity** (`#lage`), typed as `Organization`, carrying the laboratory name, its parent organisation (`#rit`), and a persistent institutional URL; and the **software entity** (`#Crate_Generator`), typed as `SoftwareApplication`, carrying a description, an MIT licence, and a persistent GitHub URL pointing to its source code. By being referenced from multiple data entities, these contextual entities transform a flat file listing into a rich, queryable provenance graph.


```
{
  "@id": "#lage",
  "@type": "Organization",
  "name": "Laboratory of Genomics and Epigenomics (LAGE)",
  "parentOrganization": {
    "@id": "#rit"
  },
  "url": "https://www.areasciencepark.it/en/research-infrastructures/life-sciences/lage-genomics-and-epigenomics-laboratory/"
},
{
  "@id": "#Crate_Generator",
  "@type": "SoftwareApplication",
  "creator": {
    "@id": "#lade"
  },
  "description": "Script to generate RO-Crate descriptors for lab raw data folders ",
  "license": "https://opensource.org/licenses/MIT",
  "name": "LAGE Folder Descriptor Generator",
  "url": "https://github.com/RitAreaSciencePark/LAGE_Metadata_Extraction/blob/main/Src/Crate_Generator.py"
},
}
```

Figure 1.8 Contextual entities in a LAGE RO-Crate: the organisation (`#lage`, typed `Organization`) and the crate generation software (`#Crate_Generator`, typed `SoftwareApplication`), both carrying persistent identifiers.

- **Relationships between entities:** The RO-Crate model explicitly encodes relationships between data and contextual entities using typed Schema.org properties. In the LAGE crate, the key relationships are: `hasPart` (folder-to-file containment); `creator` (file-to-organisation attribution); `wasGeneratedBy` (file-to-software provenance), and `actionProcess` (file-to-sequencing-activity linkage). Together, these typed properties form a directed graph encoding the complete provenance of the dataset in machine-traversable form, as illustrated conceptually in the provenance chain example presented in [subsection 1.4.2](#).

Storage, Portability, and Relationship to This Work

RO-Crates can be stored locally, archived as ZIP or BagIt, published on Zenodo, or hosted on the web — all without modifying the crate structure. This flexibility is directly relevant to LAGE, where datasets must be shareable with collaborators, depositable in DECOS, and archivable under the ten-year retention requirement. [Table 1.2](#) maps RO-Crate structural features to the FAIR sub-principles they satisfy.

Table 1.2 *Relationship between FAIR principles and RO-Crate implementation features.*

FAIR Pillar	FAIR Requirement	RO-Crate Implementation
Findable	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● F1: Unique identifiers● F2: Rich metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Each entity assigned a unique <code>@id</code> as IRI● Schema.org-typed entities with descriptive metadata● Machine-indexable JSON-LD structure
Accessible	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● A1.1: Open protocol● A2: Persistent metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Metadata represented in standard JSON-LD● Portable as folder or ZIP archive● Metadata accessible independently of data files
Interoperable	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● I1: Shared vocabulary● I3: Qualified references	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Schema.org vocabulary declared in <code>@context</code>● Typed semantic relations: <code>wasGeneratedBy</code>, <code>actionProcess</code>● JSON-LD enables semantic interoperability
Reusable	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● R1.1: Licence● R1.2: Provenance● R1.3: Community standards	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● MIT licence URI declared in root entity● Provenance captured via <code>wasGeneratedBy</code> and <code>actionProcess</code>● Compliance with RO-Crate 1.2 specification

1.5 Overview of the Proposed Pipeline

Three key challenges were identified at LAGE (subsection 1.3.4): heterogeneous metadata formats, absence of sample tracking, and long-term reproducibility risk. These collectively motivate the development of an automated solution operating at the intersection of the FAIR principles and the RO-Crate standard introduced in this chapter.

To address these requirements, this work develops a modular and automated Python pipeline for metadata extraction, normalisation, and packaging. The system inspects instrument-native

files, automatically detects their type through content-based analysis, extracts relevant metadata, and converts it into a standardised JSON representation. The resulting metadata is then packaged using the RO-Crate framework, producing self-describing, FAIR-compliant research objects ready for deposit and long-term reuse.

A central design objective is the elimination of manual intervention. Rather than relying on user-defined input types, the system employs a content-based detection mechanism that identifies file formats regardless of naming conventions or directory organisation, ensuring robust classification across the full heterogeneous output of LAGE.

The pipeline is structured around a **modular architecture** inspired by the Registry Pattern: each file format is handled by a dedicated extractor module registered within a central engine. Adding support for a new instrument requires only the implementation of a new module, without modifying the core processing logic, ensuring long-term scalability. The materials, implementation details, and validation of this pipeline are presented in [Chapter 2](#).

Chapter Summary

This chapter established the scientific and technical foundations of this work. It introduced high-throughput sequencing technologies, the data formats they produce, and the critical role of structured metadata in ensuring long-term data usability. The data management challenges at LAGE were examined and mapped onto specific FAIR principle violations. The FAIR framework and the RO-Crate standard were then presented as the conceptual and practical pillars of the solution developed in this work, whose implementation is detailed in [Chapter 2](#).

Chapter 2

Materials, Methods and Pipeline Design

Chapter Overview

This chapter presents the materials and methods of the automated metadata extraction pipeline. It first describes the case study datasets provided by LAGE and the heterogeneous file types produced across their sequencing workflows. It then details the pipeline architecture: content-based file detection, specialised extractor modules, the JSON metadata schema, and utility modules for sample tracking and lineage reconstruction. The chapter concludes with the FAIR packaging layer, describing how extracted metadata is assembled into RO-Crate compliant research objects.

2.1 Case Study Datasets

The pipeline was developed and validated using three case study datasets provided by LAGE, each originating from a distinct sequencing platform: Illumina NovaSeq6000 (ORID0087), Oxford Nanopore PromethION 24 (ORID0085), and Illumina BeadStudio (ORID0036). Together, these datasets cover a representative range of the file formats, naming conventions, and directory structures encountered in routine sequencing operations at LAGE, spanning three major instrument families, and collectively define the scope of the pipeline’s extraction and standardisation capabilities.

The two sequencing datasets (ORID0087 and ORID0085) follow a common four-phase experimental workflow:

1. Sample reception and registration;
2. Pre-sequencing quality control;
3. Sequencing configuration and data generation;
4. Post-sequencing processing and quality control.

The BeadStudio dataset (ORID0036) follows a distinct microarray scanning workflow described separately in [subsection 2.1.3](#).

2.1.1 ORID0087 – IlluminaNovaSeq6000

The ORID0087 dataset originates from a short-read amplicon sequencing project conducted on the Illumina NovaSeq6000 platform (experiment identifier: 20260130_ORID0087_C), applied

to agricultural samples targeting two amplicon markers in parallel: bacterial 16S rRNA and fungal ITS. Each target produces an independent set of demultiplexed FASTQ files and quality control outputs, organised under `ORID0087-02-16S/` and `ORID0087-02-ITS/` respectively. The dataset spans five top-level components: a sample reception sheet (`SampleSheet.xlsx`), a pre-sequencing quality control directory (`QualityCheckBeforeRun/`), a sequencing configuration file (`20260129_ORID0087_C_ALL_INDEXES.csv`), and two post-sequencing result directories, generating a combined total of 388 FastQC reports and 3 representative FASTQ files (included as illustrative samples) across both targets.

Sample Reception Phase

Samples are received at LAGE in a 96-well plate format. The primary file associated with this phase is an Excel spreadsheet, typically generated either by the researcher or, in the case of external service requests, by the client.

This file contains two main sheets:

- **Samples** sheet: This sheet provides a comprehensive list of samples used for metagenomic (bacterial 16S) and fungal (ITS) analyses. Each sample is described using the following metadata fields: *Sample code*; *Sample_ID* (used as a key for integration with downstream quality control and sequencing data); *Type of preparation*; *Treatment* (e.g., sugar addition); *Biological replicate*. All information contained in this sheet is considered essential and must be preserved during processing.
- **PlateScheme** sheet: This sheet describes the spatial organization of samples within the 96-well plate, providing positional context for each sample.

Data Type and Format

- **Type of Data:** Metadata
- **File Format:** `.xlsx`

Pre-Sequencing Phase

The pre-sequencing phase includes quality control procedures performed prior to sequencing, aimed at assessing the integrity and purity of the input biological material. The files generated during this phase provide both quantitative measurements and contextual metadata, which are integrated within the pipeline to support sample validation and downstream analysis. Here is a description of each of those files.

- **NanoDrop Export File (.csv):** This file contains the numerical output of UV absorbance measurements for each sample. Key columns include: *Sample.ID*: Indicates the

plate well position (e.g., A01,); *ng/μl*: Estimated DNA concentration; *260/280*: DNA/protein purity ratio (values around 1.8 indicate high DNA purity); *260/230*: Indicator of potential contamination (ideal values range between 2.0 and 2.2). These measurements are critical for evaluating sample quality prior to sequencing and may influence downstream decisions, such as sample inclusion or repetition. Additional columns (typically spanning wavelengths from 220 to 360 nm) report absorbance values across the spectrum; however, these are not directly used in the current processing workflow.

- **NanoDrop Spectral Report (.pdf)**: This file complements the numerical data contained in the CSV file by providing a visual representation (spectral curves) of the absorbance spectra for each sample.
- **Sample Report File (.csv)**: This file is manually generated to document technical observations and anomalies identified during both pre-sequencing and post-sequencing stages. It serves as a tracking tool for samples exhibiting issues, enabling the recording of critical events and operational decisions throughout the workflow.
- **Image Files (.jpeg)**: These files provide visual documentation of sample conditions (e.g., plate images), supporting the identification and traceability of problematic samples referenced in the sample report file.

Data Type and Format:

- **Type of Data**: Quantitative measurements and metadata.
- **File Format**: .csv, .pdf, .jpeg.

Sequencing Phase

The sequencing phase is associated with the generation of configuration files used to define the run parameters and enable sample identification during data processing. This phase is done by using Illumina NovaSeq 6000 platform. The main files associated to this phase are:

- **Sequencing Configuration File (.csv)**: This file contains the run setup information required for sequencing and downstream demultiplexing. It defines the association between biological samples and their corresponding index sequences.

The table typically includes the following key elements: *Sample identifiers*: Unique labels assigned to each sample; *Plate position*: Well location used to maintain consistency with upstream sample tracking; *Index sequences (i7 and i5)*: Barcodes used for sample multiplexing and read assignment during demultiplexing; *Project reference*: Identifier linking samples to a specific sequencing project.

In the considered datasets, the same set of samples is used for multiple sequencing targets, such as 16S rRNA (bacterial profiling) and ITS (fungal profiling), typically organized in distinct sections within the file.

- **Base Call (BCL) files**: Those files represent the raw data generated by the sequencing instrument Illumina NovaSeq 6000, which contain base-by-base sequencing information.

Data Type and Format

- **Type of Data:** Sequencing configuration metadata and raw sequencing data.
- **File Formats:** `.csv` (configuration), `BCL` (raw sequencing output).

Post-Sequencing Phase

In the final phase, raw `BCL` data are demultiplexed and converted into `FASTQ` format using `bcl2fastq`, guided by the index sequences defined in the sequencing configuration file ([subsubsection 2.1.1](#)). Each read is assigned to its corresponding sample, producing one pair of compressed `FASTQ` files per sample (`R1` and `R2` for paired-end sequencing), stored in `.fastq.gz` format.

Following demultiplexing, a two-level quality control workflow is applied independently for each sequencing target:

- **FastQC** (version 0.12.1) is run on each `FASTQ` file, producing one `.html` report and one `.zip` archive per file, covering per-base quality scores, sequence composition, GC content, adapter contamination, and duplication levels;
- **MultiQC** aggregates all individual `FastQC` outputs into a single interactive `multiqc_report.html` and a structured `multiqc_data/` directory containing per-metric summaries in `.txt`, `.json`, and `.parquet` formats.

This QC structure is replicated independently for each sequencing target, resulting in two parallel output directories: `ORID0087-02-16S/` for bacterial community profiling (16S rRNA) and `ORID0087-02-ITS/` for fungal community characterisation (ITS).

Data Type and Format

- **Type of Data:** Demultiplexed sequencing reads and aggregated quality control reports.
- **File Formats:** `.fastq.gz` (sequencing reads), `.zip` (FastQC reports), `.html`, `.txt`, `.json`, `.parquet` (MultiQC reports and data).

2.1.2 ORID0085 – Oxford Nanopore PromethION

The `ORID0085` dataset originates from a long-read sequencing project conducted on the Oxford Nanopore PromethION 24 platform (experiment identifier: `20250929_ORID0085C`). It comprises two samples (`Pich31-12-24` and `LIS14-11-24`), each sequenced on an independent flow cell within the same instrument run. For the purposes of this evaluation, a representative subset of the full dataset was used: all metadata and configuration files are included in

their entirety, while only a small number of raw data files (POD5 and FASTQ) are retained as illustrative samples. This subset of 34 files preserves the complete structural and metadata heterogeneity of the original dataset while keeping the evaluation tractable. Files are organised in a deeply nested directory structure reflecting the MinKNOW output hierarchy, with instrument-specific identifiers embedded in filenames (e.g., PBE45781_84291f8c_26f25936).

Pre-Sequencing Quality Control Phase

Prior to sequencing, sample quality was assessed using a **TapeStation** electrophoresis system. This instrument produces three output files:

- **Sample Table (.csv):** Contains per-sample quantitative measurements including well position, DNA Integrity Number (DIN), concentration in ng/ μ L, sample description, and alert flags indicating instrument (e.g., expired ScreenTape device);
- **Compact Peak Table (.csv):** Records electrophoretic peak data for each sample, used to assess fragment size distribution;
- **TapeStation Report (.pdf):** A visual report providing electropherogram traces and summary statistics for all samples in the run.

Data Type and Format

- **Type of Data:** Pre-sequencing quality control measurements.
- **File Formats:** .csv, .pdf.

Sequencing Phase

Each sample was sequenced on a dedicated PromethION 24 flow cell (FLO-PRO114M) using the SQK-LSK114 library preparation kit and the `sequencing_PRO114_DNA_e8_2_400K` sequencing protocol, managed through the MinKNOW software. Runs were initiated on 2025-09-29 and completed on 2025-10-02, spanning approximately 72 hours each. The primary configuration and instrument metadata files produced per run are:

- **Sample Sheet (.csv):** Records the run configuration including `protocol_run_id`, `position_id`, `flow_cell_id`, `sample_id`, `experiment_id`, `flow_cell_product_code`, and sequencing kit;
- **Final Summary (.txt):** A plain-text file generated at run completion by MinKNOW, recording instrument identifier, flow cell identifier, run and acquisition identifiers, start and stop timestamps, basecalling status, and file counts for POD5 and FASTQ outputs;

- **Run Report (.md, .html):** Human-readable run reports generated by MinKNOW providing detailed run statistics, QC metrics, and throughput summaries;
- **Sequencing Summary (.txt):** A per-read tabular file recording read-level metrics including read identifiers, durations, lengths, and quality scores.

In addition, the following instrument diagnostic files are produced within an `other_reports/` subdirectory:

- **Throughput Report (.csv):** Time-series data recording the number of reads, base-called bases, and estimated yield at regular intervals throughout the run;
- **Pore Activity Report (.csv):** Time-series data recording the state of each nanopore channel (e.g., adapter, sequencing, inactive) across the run duration;
- **Pore Scan Data (.csv):** Results of the pre-run pore scan assessing flow cell quality;
- **Temperature Adjustment Data (.csv):** Records thermal regulation events during the run, including target and measured temperatures;
- **Barcode Alignment (.tsv):** Records barcode assignment statistics including alias, type, and acquisition run identifier per barcode.

Data Type and Format

- **Type of Data:** Sequencing configuration metadata, run statistics, and instrument diagnostics.
- **File Formats:** .csv, .tsv, .txt, .md, .html, .json.

Post-Sequencing Phase

Raw ionic current signals are stored in **POD5** format files within the `pod5/` subdirectory. Basecalling is performed using the **Dorado** basecaller, producing:

- **FASTQ files (passed, fastq_pass/):** Sequence reads that meet the minimum quality threshold, stored in compressed `.fastq.gz` format;
- **FASTQ files (failed, fastq_fail/):** Reads that did not meet the quality threshold, retained for diagnostic purposes;
- **Sequence Summary (.txt):** A summary file produced by the basecaller recording per-read statistics from the basecalling process;
- **Basecaller Log (.log):** A timestamped log file recording the basecalling execution, software version, and processing events.

Data Type and Format

- **Type of Data:** Raw sequencing signals and basecalled sequence data.
- **File Formats:** .pod5, .fastq.gz, .txt, .log.

2.1.3 ORID0036 – BeadStudio Illumina iScan

The BeadStudio dataset originates from a DNA methylation profiling project conducted using the Illumina Infinium MethylationEPIC v2 array platform (project identifier: 20250219_ORID0036_NEUROMED_EPIC), applied to human samples. Unlike the two sequencing datasets, this workflow does not involve library preparation, sequencing chemistry, or FASTQ generation. DNA is instead hybridised to EPIC BeadChip arrays and scanned using the Illumina iScan system, which measures fluorescence intensity at over 900.000 CpG probe positions per sample. The representative dataset comprises CSV sample sheets spanning scanning batches from February to December 2025, all using the same manifest (EPIC-8v2-0_A2.bpm), confirming uniform array chemistry across the project. The absence of pre-scanning QC files, post-processing outputs, and IDAT files distinguishes this workflow structurally from ORID0087 and ORID0085, illustrating a third category of metadata heterogeneity that the pipeline must handle.

The dataset consists exclusively of **84 BeadStudio sample sheet CSV files**, organised under a single CSVs/ subdirectory. Each file corresponds to one scanning batch and follows a consistent three-section structure:

- **[Header]:** records the investigator name, project name, experiment name, and scanning date (e.g., DATE, 20250227);
- **[Manifests]:** specifies the BeadChip array manifest file used for probe mapping (e.g., EPIC-8v2-0_A2.bpm);
- **[Data]:** contains one row per sample, with fields `Sample_Name`, `Sample_Plate`, `Sample_Well`, `Sample_Group`, `Pool_ID`, `Sentrix_ID` (BeadChip serial number), and `Sentrix_Position` (array row and column, e.g., R01C01).

These sample sheets serve simultaneously as scanning configuration inputs for the iScan instrument and as the primary metadata documents for each array batch. The primary data output of the scanning process (IDAT files containing raw fluorescence intensity values) is stored separately and is not included in this dataset. The pipeline therefore targets these CSV files as the sole metadata source for the BeadStudio workflow.

Data Type and Format

- **Type of Data:** Array scanning configuration and sample metadata.
- **File Format:** .csv (BeadStudio sample sheets).

In this project, the dataset comprises a heterogeneous and substantial collection of files originating from multiple sequencing runs.¹ These files are typically organized within deeply nested directory structures and are stored in the [ORFEO data center](#). This diversity in file formats, structures, and storage organization reflects real-world laboratory conditions and highlights the need for automated mechanisms capable of detecting, processing, and standardizing metadata at scale. To fulfill those requirements, the following section introduces the proposed automated solution.

2.2 Pipeline Architecture and Implementation

The pipeline is implemented in Python and follows a modular and structured processing logic that ensures consistent handling of all heterogeneous input files, regardless of their origin or format.

2.2.1 The Four-Step Processing Workflow

The pipeline follows a structured four-step workflow, illustrated conceptually in [Figure 2.2](#).

Figure 2.1 *Modular Python Pipeline: Technical Workflow.*

¹Exact counts may vary depending on the project scope and data availability.

Step 1: Input

The system accepts both individual files and batch directories containing heterogeneous data. Supported formats include, but are not limited to, `.csv`, `.bam`, `.xlsx`, `.fastq` and `.pod5`. When a directory is provided, the pipeline recursively scans all subdirectories to identify processable files.

Step 2: Auto-Detection

Each file is passed through a content-based detection engine. This engine sequentially evaluates validation functions associated with registered extractor modules. Detection is based on file structure and content rather than file extensions alone, ensuring robustness against inconsistent naming.

Step 3: Extraction

Once a file type is identified, the corresponding extractor processes it through a standardized extraction interface, implemented through the function `one_single_file()`. This function encapsulates format-specific logic while ensuring that all extractors return metadata in a consistent internal structure.

Step 4: Output

The extracted metadata is normalized and converted into a structured JSON format. In addition, the pipeline generates summary reports detailing successfully processed files, skipped files, and potential errors encountered during execution.

While the four-step workflow describes the logical progression of data through the system, its practical implementation relies on a modular software architecture that separates detection, extraction, and metadata generation into specialized components. This architecture also enables flexible file handling, scalable processing, and seamless integration of new formats. The following section details how these components interact to operationalize the workflow.

2.2.2 Modular Architecture: Specialized Extraction and Management

The pipeline is designed using a modular architecture that separates responsibilities across dedicated components, each responsible for a specific stage of file detection, metadata extraction, lineage reconstruction, or FAIR packaging.

The Core Architectural Components are:

Figure 2.2 Pipeline Modular Core Architecture.

The Centralized Management Engine

The pipeline orchestration is managed by the `Main_Auto_Processor.py` script, which acts as the central management engine. It coordinates file detection, routing, and metadata extraction across heterogeneous inputs.

Processing Workflow

For each input file, the system follows a structured processing sequence:

1. **Validation:** the system follows a structured sequence based on a **validation polling strategy**, where each registered extractor exposes a validation function describing its expected file structure. These functions are iteratively evaluated until a match is found.
2. **Selection and Routing:** The module whose validation criteria are satisfied is selected and the file is automatically routed for processing. This approach enables flexible and dynamic format recognition.
3. **Extraction:** Metadata is parsed and structured into a standardized json format.
4. **Fallback:** If no extractor module validates the input file, the system does not terminate execution. Instead, a fallback mechanism logs a warning and skips the file, ensuring

robustness and preventing pipeline failure when encountering unknown or unsupported formats.

Inputs and Outputs

The input requirements and generated outputs are defined as follows.

Inputs:

- Single file or directory containing nested data.

Outputs:

- Standardized JSON files containing structured metadata such as sample identifiers, file types, project identifiers and extracted attributes.
- Summary reports describing processed, skipped, and unsupported files generated during pipeline execution.

Usage

The execution modes supported by the module are described below.

Batch mode:

```
python3 ./Src/Main_Auto_Processor.py <input_folder> <output_folder> --batch
```

Single file:

```
python3 ./Src/Main_Auto_Processor.py <input_file.csv> <output_folder>
```

Specialized Extractor Modules

The pipeline incorporates a library of specialized extractor modules designed to process heterogeneous file formats generated by different sequencing instruments and laboratory workflows. Given the high variability and inconsistency of real-world data (e.g., non-standardized file naming, nested directory structures), these modules rely on content-based validation rather than filename conventions, ensuring robust and flexible format recognition. In particular, to ensure interoperability and seamless integration within the system, all modules adhere to the following consistent internal structure:

- `is_valid_type(file_path)`: Defines content-based validation logic used to identify whether a given file matches the expected structure of the module, independently of

file naming conventions. This function enables reliable format detection in real-world scenarios where file naming conventions are often inconsistent or unreliable, significantly increasing pipeline robustness.

- `one_single_file(...)`: Implements the core extraction logic for processing an individual file, parsing relevant information and returning metadata according to a standardized internal schema to ensure consistency and interoperability across heterogeneous data source.

BeadStudio Extractor (`Extractor_BeadStudio.py`)

Core Functionality

This module extracts metadata from Illumina BeadStudio sample sheet CSV files produced by the iScan microarray scanner. Validation is performed by scanning the first 20 lines of the file for the keyword `BeadStudio`. The module parses three named sections: `[Header]` (project name, experiment name, scanning date), `[Manifests]` (array manifest identifier, e.g., `EPIC-8v2-0_A2.bpm`), and `[Data]` (one record per sample including `Sample_Name`, `Sentrix_ID`, and `Sentrix_Position`). The ORID identifier is extracted from the filename using a regular expression pattern (`ORID\d{4}`).

JSON output structure — `Extractor_BeadStudio.py`

```
{ "instrument_type": "Illumina_iScan",
  "phase_workflow": "sequencing",
  "file_name": "20250219_sample_sheet.csv",
  "file_path": "/data/ORID0036/CSVs/...",
  "file_description": "BeadStudio sample sheet containing
                      array scanning configuration",
  "metadata": { "investigator_name": "...",
                "experiment_name": "...",
                "date": "2025-02-19",
                "manifest_id": "EPIC-8v2-0_A2.bpm" },
  "samples": [{"sample_id": "...",
               "sample_name": "...",
               "sentrix_id": "..."}
             ]
}
```

Extractor_IlluminaSampleSheet.py

Core Functionality

This module processes Illumina sample sheet CSV files generated during sequencing runs on the NovaSeq6000 platform. These files are organised into structured sections: `[Header]`,

[Reads], [Settings], and [Data], and contain the essential information required to link raw sequencing output files (FASTQ) to their corresponding biological samples. Validation is performed by inspecting the first 20 lines of the file and requiring the simultaneous presence of [Header], Workflow, GenerateFASTQ, and Chemistry, Amplicon. This three-condition check ensures that only amplicon sequencing run sheets are matched, distinguishing them from Bead-Studio files which share the [Header] structure but carry different workflow and chemistry identifiers.

JSON output — Extractor_IlluminaSampleSheet.py

```
{ "instrument_type": "Illumina_NovaSeq6000",
  "phase_workflow": "sequencing",
  "file_name": "SampleSheet_ORID0087.csv",
  "file_path": "/data/ORID0087/...",
  "file_description": "Illumina sequencing configuration
                      file defining run parameters,
                      index sequences, and
                      sample-to-barcode mapping",
  "metadata": { "investigator_name": "...",
                "experiment_name": "20260129_ORID0087_C",
                "date": "2026-01-29",
                "workflow": "GenerateFASTQ",
                "chemistry": "Amplicon" },
  "samples": [ { "sample_id": "...",
                 "sample_name": "...",
                 "index_i7": "ATCGATCG",
                 "index_i5": "GCTAGCTA",
                 "well_position": "A01"
               }
            ]
}
```

Extractor_NanoDrop_QC.py

Core Functionality

Extracts quantitative quality control measurements from NanoDrop UV absorbance spectrophotometer export CSV files. Validation checks for the four required column headers: Sample.ID, ng.ul, 260.280, and 260.230. During extraction, column names are normalised: Sample.ID is renamed to Sample_ID (resolving the dot-to-underscore inconsistency between NanoDrop and Illumina sample sheet conventions), and the remaining columns are mapped to concentration_ng_ul, ratio_260_280, and ratio_260_230. All spectral columns spanning 220 to 360 nm are discarded as they are not used downstream. The output also records the quality interpretation thresholds applied.

JSON output — Extractor_NanoDrop_QC.py

```
{ "instrument_type": "NanoDrop_Spectrophotometer",
  "phase_workflow": "pre_sequencing_qc",
  "file_name": "NanoDrop_ORID0087.csv",
  "file_path": "/data/ORID0087/...",
  "file_description": "NanoDrop UV absorbance export
                      containing per-sample DNA
                      concentration and purity ratios",
  "metadata": {"quality_thresholds": {
    "ratio_260_280_min": 1.8,
    "ratio_260_280_max": 2.0,
    "ratio_260_230_min": 2.0 },
    "total_samples": 24 },
  "samples": [ { "sample_id": "A01",
    "concentration_ng_ul": 45.2,
    "ratio_260_280": 1.89,
    "ratio_260_230": 2.01,
    "sample_observations": ... } ]
}
```

Extractor_TapeStation.py

Core Functionality

Extracts pre-sequencing quality control data from Agilent TapeStation Analysis PDF reports. Validation uses the `pdfplumber` library to read the first page of the PDF and checks for the signature string "TapeStation Analysis Software". The module iterates over all pages, extracts tables, and identifies the Sample Table by checking for the presence of Well and DIN column headers. Extracted fields are normalised to `well`, `din_score`, `concentration_ng_ul`, and `sample_observations`. The module also records the software version and DIN quality threshold (DIN \geq 7.0 for high integrity DNA).

JSON output — Extractor_TapeStation.py

```
{ "instrument_type": "Agilent_TapeStation",
  "phase_workflow": "pre_sequencing_qc",
  "file_name": "2025-03-13_ext_lupo_05x.pdf",
  "file_path": "/data/ORID0085/...",
  "file_description": "Agilent TapeStation electrophoresis
                      report containing per-sample DIN
                      scores and DNA integrity assessments",
  "metadata": { "instrument": "TapeStation 4200",
    "software": "Agilent TapeStation 4.1",
    "total_wells_processed": 24,
  }
}
```



```
        "qc_metrics": {"din_threshold": 7.0,  
                      "alert_description": "DIN below threshold"}}  
    ,  
    "samples": [ { "sample_id": "A01",  
                  "sample_name": "...",  
                  "din_score": 8.2,  
                  "concentration": 45.0,  
                  "alert": "..."} ]  
}
```

Extractor_Nanopore.py

Core Functionality

Handles the full heterogeneous output of a MinKNOW PromethION sequencing run. Unlike all other extractor modules, which produce one JSON file per input file, this module implements an incremental aggregation strategy: rather than producing a single flat output, it maintains one consolidated file per sample — named *Nanopore_sample_id_Generalized_metadata.json* — that is updated each time a new file belonging to that sample is processed. This design reflects the fact that a Nanopore run produces dozens of files that collectively describe a single sequencing event, and no single file contains the complete run metadata. Sample identity is resolved automatically from the directory structure: MinKNOW organises its output under an experiment folder whose name follows the YYYYMMDD_ date prefix convention; the subdirectory immediately beneath it is taken as the sample name (e.g. Pich31-12-24, LIS14-11-24). When the *final_summary* or *sample_sheet* file is encountered, the *sample_id* field it contains is additionally stored inside the JSON record, providing a human-readable cross-reference.

The module identifies nine distinct Nanopore file sub-types by inspecting file extensions and content headers:

- **sample_sheet** (.csv with `protocol_run_id` header): run configuration, sample and flow cell identifiers;
- **final_summary** (*final_summary*.txt*): instrument ID, timestamps, file counts;
- **sequencing_summary** (*sequencing_summary*.txt*): per-read statistics including total reads, pass/fail counts, mean Q-score, unique run IDs;
- **pore_activity** (.csv with `channel state` header): time-series pore state data aggregated by channel state;
- **throughput** (.csv with `experiment time` header): cumulative read and base yield at run completion;
- **temperature** (.csv with `current_target_temperature` header): thermal control data including target temperature and sequencing speed;
- **pore_scan** (.csv with `mux_scan_assessment` header): pre-run flow cell health statistics (available pores, saturated wells);
- **report_in_markdown** (*report*.md*): tracking ID metadata extracted from JSON block embedded in the Markdown report;

- `json_report` (`report*.json`): instrument host information.

A single `Generalized_metadata.json` per run is produced incrementally as each MinKNOW output file is processed.

JSON output — `Extractor_Nanopore.py`

```
{ "instrument_type": "Oxford_Nanopore_PromethION",
  "phase_workflow": "sequencing",
  "file_name": "Nanopore_LIS14-11-24_Generalized_metadata.json",
  "file_path": "/data/ORID0085/...",
  "file_description": "Consolidated Nanopore run metadata
                      aggregated from MinKNOW output
                      files across the sequencing run",
  "run_id": "84291f8c-b7a7-4891-90bb-8f68c00020fe",
  "sample_id": "LIS14-11-24",
  "metadata": { "throughput": {
                "total_reads": 9752977,
                "passed_reads": 3664506,
                "bases": 5519738962,
                "run_time_minutes": 597 },
  "metadata_Sample_Sheet": {"flow_cell_id": "PBE45781",
                            "sample_id": "Pich31-12-24",
                            "experiment_id": "20250929_ORID0085C",
                            "kit": null},
  "metadata_Sequencing_Summary": { "total_reads": 49,
                                   "passed_filtering_count": 4,
                                   "mean_qscore": 3.43,
                                   "unique_samples": ["LIS14-11-24"] },
  "pore_scan_diagnostics": { "available_pores": 105,
                              "saturated_wells": 89,
                              "total_wells": 299} },
  "samples": [],
  "files_processed": [ "
    sample_sheet_PBE45781_20250929_1357_84291f8c.csv",
    "final_summary_PBE45781_84291f8c_26f25936.txt",
    "sequencing_summary_PBE45781_84291f8c_26f25936.txt",
    "throughput_PBE45781_84291f8c_26f25936.csv",
    "pore_scan_data_PBE45781_84291f8c_26f25936.csv" ]
}
```

`Extractor_FastQC.py`

Core Functionality

Extracts quality control metrics from FastQC output ZIP archives. Validation checks that the file ends with `_fastqc.zip` or contains `fastqc_data.txt` internally. The module extracts

the archive into a temporary directory, parses `fastqc_data.txt` using regular expressions to retrieve the FastQC version, total sequence count, sequence length range, GC percentage, and encoding. A distinctive feature of this module is its **provenance tracking mechanism**: it locates the originating FASTQ file and computes its MD5 checksum, storing both the file path and checksum in a `derived_from` field. This provides a cryptographic link between the QC report and the data it describes, directly satisfying FAIR sub-principle R1.2.

JSON output — `Extractor_FastQC.py`

```
{ "instrument_type": "FastQC_Babraham",
  "phase_workflow": "post_sequencing_qc",
  "file_name": "sample_A01_fastqc.zip",
  "file_path": "/data/ORID0087/FastQC/...",
  "file_description": "FastQC quality control report
                      archive containing per-read
                      quality metrics derived from
                      a FASTQ file",
  "metadata": { "tool": "FastQC",
                "version": "0.12.1",
                "total_sequences": 150000,
                "sequence_length": "151",
                "gc_percent": 48,
                "encoding": "Sanger / Illumina 1.9"},
  "derived_from": {
    "fastq_file_name": "sample_A01.fastq.gz",
    "fastq_path": "/data/ORID0087/FASTQ/...",
    "fastq_checksum_md5": "d41d8cd98f00b204e9800998ecf8427e" }
}
```

`Extractor_Thermal_Report.py`

Core Functionality

This module processes thermal cycler report CSV files generated by PCR instruments during the library preparation phase. These reports are characterised by semi-structured and inconsistently formatted outputs, combining filename-derived metadata with content-based validation to recover structured information reliably. Validation checks that the first line starts with `Side` and that the third line contains `Time,Current Cycle`, ensuring robust identification regardless of filename conventions. Instrument identifier, run side, and date are extracted directly from the filename using a regular expression (e.g., `A00618_Right_2024-01-19.csv`), while the module applies column remapping strategies to extract relevant metadata such as amplification parameters and run conditions. The total number of data points is recorded without loading the full dataset, keeping the output compact and ensuring compatibility with the downstream metadata integration framework of the pipeline.

JSON output — `Extractor_Thermal_Report.py`

```
{ "instrument_type": "Illumina_NovaSeq6000",
  "phase_workflow": "sequencing",
  "file_name": "A00618_Thermal_Report_20260129.csv",
  "file_path": "/data/ORID0087/...",
  "file_description": "PCR thermal cycler report recording
                      amplification parameters and
                      run conditions",
  "metadata": { "instrument_id": "A00618",
                "run_side": "A",
                "run_date": "2026-01-29",
                "number_of_data_points": 120,
                "columns_details": { "0": "Cycle",
                                     "1": "Temperature",
                                     "2": "Time" } }
}
```

`Extractor_FMGeneration.py` and `Extractor_FMAutoTilt.py`

Prior to each sequencing run, the Illumina NovaSeq6000 performs pre-run optical calibration procedures relevant to this pipeline. **Focus Model Generation** uses the onboard Focus Tracking Module (FTM) to construct a per-surface optical model mapping objective lens position to image sharpness across the flow cell, producing one report per surface containing instrument metadata, focus model parameters, and per-position quality metrics. **AutoTilt** verifies and corrects the angular alignment of the flow cell relative to the optical axis, recording tilt measurements and correction parameters across a through-focus stack. Both are instrument maintenance outputs stored alongside sequencing files; their inclusion in the pipeline ensures the complete instrument state at run time is captured, supporting long-term reproducibility and troubleshooting.

Core Functionality

`Extractor_FMGeneration.py` validates input files by checking for `Instrument Name` in the first line. It applies a dynamic multi-section extraction strategy: top-level metadata appearing before the first bracketed section header (instrument name, date) is extracted into a `metadata` dictionary, while each named section (e.g., `[FocusModel Red]`, `[FocusModel Input Green]`) is extracted as a separate key in the output JSON. Two-column sections (label-value pairs such as focus model summary statistics) are stored as lists of dictionaries; multi-column sections (per-position coordinate tables) are stored as lists of row records. The ORID identifier is extracted from the filename where present.

`Extractor_FMAutoTilt.py` validates input files by checking that the first line starts with `[FTM Through-Focus Stack]`. It applies the same dynamic section extraction logic, capturing all bracketed sections including tilt position tables and focus stack results. Instrument

ID, date, and time are parsed directly from the filename using a regular expression (e.g., A00618_2024-01-19_15-59-34_FM-AutoTilt_Report.csv).

JSON output — Extractor_FMGeneration.py

```
{ "instrument_type": "Illumina_NovaSeq6000",
  "phase_workflow": "sequencing",
  "file_name": "A00618_FM-Generation_Report.csv",
  "file_path": "/data/ORID0087/...",
  "file_description": "Illumina NovaSeq6000 focus model
                      generation report produced during
                      pre-run optical calibration",
  "metadata": { "instrument_name": "A00618", "date": "2026-01-29"
                , "focusmodel_red": [{"Focus Height": 1200.5, "Model Quality"
                                     : 0.98}, {"Focus Height": 1201.0, "Model Quality": 0.97} ]
                , "focusmodel_input_green": [{"X": 0, "Y": 0, "FocusScore": 0.
                                               95}, {"X": 1, "Y": 0, "FocusScore": 0.97} ]
              }
```

JSON output — Extractor_FMAutoTilt.py

```
{ "instrument_type": "Illumina_NovaSeq6000",
  "phase_workflow": "sequencing",
  "file_name": "A00618_FM-AutoTilt_Report.csv",
  "file_path": "/data/ORID0087/...",
  "file_description": "Illumina NovaSeq6000 AutoTilt calibration
                      report recording flow cell angular
                      alignment corrections",
  "metadata": { "instrument_name": "A00618",
                "date": "2026-01-29" },
  "autotilt_data": [ { "Focus Height": 1200.5,
                      "Tilt X": 0.002, "Tilt Y": -0.001,
                      "Correction": 0.003},
                    { "Focus Height": 1201.0,
                      "Tilt X": 0.001, "Tilt Y": -0.002,
                      "Correction": 0.002 } ]
}
```

Utility Modules for Data Lineage and Traceability

In high-throughput sequencing environments, metadata describing a single sample or project is rarely contained within a single file. Instead, it is distributed across heterogeneous file formats and deeply nested directory structures, where the relationships between samples, processing steps, and generated outputs are often not explicitly preserved. This fragmentation leads to potential loss of contextual information, reduced reproducibility, and an inability to reconstruct

the complete history of a sample across multiple runs or platforms — precisely the challenge identified in [subsection 1.3.4](#).

To address this, the pipeline includes two dedicated utility modules designed to reconstruct data provenance by identifying, aggregating, and organising metadata across multiple sources. Together, they enable reliable cross-file sample tracking, support auditing workflows, and ensure that the relationships between samples and their associated processing steps are preserved in a structured, machine-readable form. The following subsections describe each module in detail.

Recursive ORID Extractor

The `Extractor_Orid_Recursively.py` module is designed to process files associated with a specific project identifier (ORID). It enables robust retrieval of project-related data by combining direct filename matching with recursive directory traversal across nested directory structures. This approach reflects real-world data organization in sequencing environments, where relevant files are often distributed across multiple levels of storage.

Core Functionality

- Recursive navigation through all nested subdirectories starting from a given input folder;
- Identification of files using a dual-layer matching strategy:
 - **Direct filename matching:** detection of ORID within filenames (e.g., `ORID0036_data.csv`);
 - **Directory-based inheritance:** identification of files located within folder structures associated with the ORID (e.g., `post_run/ORID0036/CSVs/data.csv`).
- Integration with the `Main_Auto_Processor` for validation and metadata extraction;
- Flattening of generated JSON outputs into a single target directory.

Processing Workflow

For a given ORID, the module follows a structured process:

1. **Scanning:** The input directory is recursively scanned to locate all candidate files;
2. **Identification:** Files are filtered based on filename matching or directory inheritance;
3. **Processing:** Identified files are passed to the main processor for validation and metadata extraction;
4. **Aggregation:** Resulting JSON files are collected and flattened into a unified output directory.

Inputs and Outputs

The following outlines the inputs and outputs of the module.

Inputs:

- Input directory containing nested project data.
- ORID identifier (e.g., `ORID0036`).

Outputs:

- Flattened JSON metadata files corresponding to the specified ORID.

Usage

The usage option is defined as follows.

```
python3 ./Src/Extractor_Orid_Recursively.py <input_folder> <ORID> <output_folder>
```

Sample History Extractor

The `Sample_History_Extractor.py` module reconstructs the **chronological sequencing history** of a given sample by aggregating its occurrences across JSON metadata files previously generated by the `Main_Auto_Processor.py` module.

Processing Workflow

For a given sample identifier, the module performs the following steps:

1. **Scanning:** The input directory is scanned to locate all JSON files;
2. **Identification:** Entries corresponding to the specified sample are extracted;
3. **Aggregation:** Metadata from multiple occurrences of the same sample is combined;
4. **Ordering:** Records are sorted chronologically to reconstruct the sample timeline;
5. **Output Generation:** A consolidated history file is produced.

Use Case and Advantages

- Enables tracking of sample re-runs over time.
- Preserves **data lineage**, capturing how a sample evolves across experiments and projects.
- Facilitates auditing, reproducibility, and downstream analytical workflows.

Inputs and Outputs

The following outlines the inputs and outputs of this module.

Inputs:

- Directory containing generated JSON metadata files.
- Sample identifier (e.g., `Sample_ID` or `Sample_Name`).

Outputs:

- Consolidated history file: `History_<SampleID>.json`.

Usage

The module can be executed as follows:

```
python3 ./Src/Sample_History_Extractor.py <json_folder> <sample_id> <output_folder>
```

FAIR Implementation and RO-Crate Packaging

Metadata is represented using JSON-LD to ensure interoperability and machine readability. This aligns with Schema.org standards and supports FAIR compliance.

RO-Crate Descriptor Generator

The `Crate_Generator.py` module generates a formal **RO-Crate** metadata descriptor (`ro-crate-metadata.json`) for all data files within a folder, independently of directory depth.

Processing Workflow

The module follows a structured process to generate a standardized RO-Crate descriptor:

1. **Scanning:** The input directory is recursively scanned to identify all files;
2. **Identification:** identified/recognised data files are selected for inclusion in the RO-Crate metadata graph;
3. **Mapping:** File locations and directory structures are encoded to preserve folder organization;
4. **Enrichment:** Institutional and provenance information is associated with each entity;
5. **Descriptor Generation:** A `ro-crate-metadata.json` file is created at the root level.

Use Case and Advantages

- Enables **FAIR compliance** by making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.
- Provides a standardized, machine-readable description of research datasets using **JSON-LD**.
- Facilitates integration with external repositories and data-sharing platforms.
- Clearly defines relationships between datasets, institutions, and processing tools.

Inputs and Outputs

The following outlines the inputs and outputs of the module.

Inputs:

- Root directory containing raw data files (recursively scanned).

Outputs:

- `ro-crate-metadata.json` descriptor file located in the root directory.

Usage

```
python3 ./Src/Crate_Generator.py <input_data_folder>
```

End-to-End RO-Crate Pipeline

The `Main_Ro-crate.py` module provides an integrated pipeline for metadata extraction and RO-Crate generation. It extends the functionality of the `Crate_Generator.py` module by incorporating the full `Main_Auto_Processor` workflow, enabling end-to-end processing from raw data to FAIR-compliant packaging.

Processing Workflow

The module performs an end-to-end sequence combining extraction and packaging:

1. **Scanning:** The input directory is recursively scanned to identify raw data files;
2. **Extraction:** Files are processed through the `Main_Auto_Processor` to generate standardized JSON metadata;
3. **Aggregation:** Generated JSON files are collected within the output directory;
4. **Packaging:** A RO-Crate descriptor is created from the resulting metadata;
5. **Output Generation:** The final `ro-crate-metadata.json` is produced alongside processed data.

Use Case and Advantages

- Provides a fully automated **end-to-end pipeline** from raw data to FAIR-compliant packaging.
- Eliminates the need for separate execution of extraction and RO-Crate generation steps.
- Ensures consistency between extracted metadata and the final RO-Crate descriptor.
- Simplifies large-scale data processing workflows in sequencing environments.

Inputs and Outputs

Inputs:

- Input directory containing raw data files.
- Output directory for generated metadata and RO-Crate packaging.

Outputs:

- Standardized JSON metadata files
- `ro-crate-metadata.json` descriptor file located in the output directory

Usage

```
python3 ./Src/Main_Ro-crate.py <input_data_folder> <output_data_folder> --batch
```

2.2.3 Performance Benchmarking Module

To support quantitative evaluation and regression testing, a dedicated benchmarking script (`benchmark_pipeline.py`) was developed alongside the pipeline. The script automates the measurement of four runtime metrics across one or more datasets.

Processing Time

The script records the wall-clock elapsed time for each pipeline execution using Python's `time.perf_counter()`, capturing both the raw value in seconds and a formatted representation in minutes and seconds.

Throughput

Throughput is calculated as the total number of input files divided by the elapsed processing time, expressed in files per second. The script also reports the breakdown between matched files (routed to an extractor) and skipped files (not recognised by any validator).

Metadata Completeness

After pipeline execution, the script opens every generated JSON output file and verifies the presence of the five universal top-level fields: `file_name`, `file_path`, `file_description`, `instrument_type`, and `phase_workflow`. It then recursively traverses all nested structures to count null, NaN, and empty string values. The completeness percentage is computed as the ratio of non-null top-level fields to the total number of fields checked.

Failure Rate

The failure rate is derived from three signals captured during execution: the pipeline return code (non-zero indicates a crash), the number of JSON output files that failed to parse, and the content of standard error output. A pipeline run is classified as failed only if the process did not exit cleanly. Files that were skipped by the fallback mechanism are not counted as failures, since skipping unrecognised files is the intended behaviour.

Usage and Output

The script can be run on a single dataset or on all three case study datasets in a single invocation:

```
python3 benchmark_pipeline.py --run-all
```

Results are printed as a summary table to the terminal and saved as a timestamped JSON report in the `Benchmark_Reports/` directory. This report provides a verifiable, machine-readable record of pipeline performance that can be attached to future releases and referenced in publications.

2.2.4 The JSON Metadata Schema

A unified top-level structure is enforced across all extractor modules, comprising five shared fields: `instrument_type`, `phase_workflow`, `file_name`, `file_path`, and `file_description`. Beyond these, the content of the `metadata` block remains module-specific, reflecting the fields available from each target file type. Two normalisation steps are implemented systematically. First, `Extractor_NanoDrop_QC.py` renames `Sample.ID` to `Sample_ID`, resolving the dot-to-underscore inconsistency between NanoDrop and Illumina sample sheet conventions. Second, `Sample_History_Extractor.py` normalises `Sample_ID` and `Sample_Name` to their lowercase equivalents (`sample_id` and `sample_name`) before writing the history file. Platform name standardisation is applied directly inside each extractor module via the `instrument_type` field, hardcoded to a canonical value aligned with the DECOS CDM `Instruments` entity.

Design Principles

The schema was designed according to four guiding principles. First, **platform independence**: field names in the schema are instrument-agnostic. Second, **minimal mandatory fields**: only fields that can be reliably extracted across all supported platforms are marked as required, avoiding systematic missing-value errors. Optional fields are included when present and silently omitted when absent. Third, **traceability**: every JSON output includes `file_name` and `file_path` fields identifying the source file processed, ensuring that the origin of each metadata record is always recoverable. Fourth, **DECOS compatibility**: the schema was designed to align with the Common Data Model (CDM) of the web app DECOS (see https://github.com/RitAreaSciencePark/decos/blob/dev/decos/decos_webapp/PRP_CDM_app/models/common_data_model.py). Key fields produced by the extractor modules, including `sample_id` (mapped to `Samples.sample_id`), `project_id` (mapped to `ServiceRequests.proposal_id`), and `instrument_platform` (mapped to `Instruments.instrument_name`), correspond directly to CDM entities, enabling structured metadata submission without manual field remapping. The schema is also designed to be **extensible**, allowing the introduction of new fields and extractor-specific attributes without breaking compatibility with existing downstream components.

Schema Structure

Each JSON output file produced by the pipeline is organised around the following top-level fields:

- **Provenance fields** — present in all outputs regardless of platform:
 - `instrument_type`: canonical instrument name aligned with the DECOS Common Data Model `Instruments` entity (e.g., `Illumina_iScan`);
 - `phase_workflow`: the sequencing workflow phase during which the file was produced (e.g., `pre_sequencing_qc`).
 - `file_name`: the basename of the input file that was processed;
 - `file_path`: the full path to the input file at the time of extraction;
 - `file_description`: a human-readable description of the file type and its role in the sequencing workflow.

The following fields are present where extractable from the input file:

- `project_id`: ORID identifier extracted from filename or header, mapping to `ServiceRequests.proposal_id` in the DECOS CDM;
 - `run_date`: run date where recorded in the input file or filename;
 - `flow_cell_id`: flow cell identifier where applicable.
- **Run fields** — extracted from instrument-native configuration files:
 - `run_id` or `experiment_name`: unique run identifier as recorded by the instrument software;

- `run_date`: run date normalised to ISO 8601 format (YYYY-MM-DD);
- `flow_cell_id`: flow cell or chip identifier where applicable;
- **Sample fields** — extracted from the data section of sample sheets:
 - `sample_id`: the primary sample identifier, normalised to a consistent format;
 - `sample_name`: human-readable sample label where available;
- **Library fields** — extracted where available from library preparation metadata:
 - `library_kit`: library preparation kit name or identifier;
 - `index_i7` / `index_i5`: index barcode sequences used for demultiplexing.
- **Quality control fields** — populated by QC-specific extractors such as `Extractor_NanoDrop_QC.py` and `Extractor_TapeStation.py`
 - `concentration_ng_ul`: concentration of the DNA or RNA in ng/μL;
 - `din_score`: DNA Integrity Number (scale of 1-10) to assess sample degradation;
 - `ratio_260_280`: purity ratio indicating the presence of protein or phenol;
 - `sample_observations`: specific alerts or warnings about the sample quality (e.g., "Expired ScreenTape").

Field Normalisation

Two categories of normalisation are implemented systematically across the pipeline.

- **Identifier normalisation** — applied at two levels. First, `Extractor_NanoDrop_QC.py` renames `Sample.ID` to `Sample_ID`, resolving the dot-to-underscore inconsistency between NanoDrop and Illumina conventions. Second, `Sample_History_Extractor.py` normalises `Sample_ID` and `Sample_Name` to their lowercase equivalents (`sample_id` and `sample_name`) before writing the history file. Prefix variations in sample identifiers are additionally handled at query time via flexible string matching: searching for `A01` will match entries recorded as `its-A01` or `16S-A01`, accommodating the platform-specific prefixes introduced during library preparation and sequencing target assignment.
- **Platform name standardisation** — applied directly inside each extractor module via the `instrument_type` field, which is hardcoded to a canonical value aligned with the DECOS CDM `Instruments` entity (e.g., `Illumina_NovaSeq6000`). This approach ensures that each module explicitly declares its instrument without relying on a centralised vocabulary lookup, making the mapping traceable and unambiguous.

Relationship to Downstream Components

The JSON schema is the interface contract that makes the rest of the pipeline possible. The `Sample_History_Extractor.py` module relies on the consistent presence of `sample_id` and `run_date` fields to aggregate records chronologically across runs. The `Crate_Generator.py`

module reads `instrument_type` and `project_id` to populate contextual entities in the RO-Crate graph. Any downstream system, including DECOS, that consumes the pipeline output can rely on these fields being present, correctly typed, and consistently named across all instruments and run types.

2.2.5 Implementation and availability details

Access to the Pipeline

The complete pipeline is publicly available through a Git-based repository hosted on GitHub, ensuring transparency, version control, and reproducibility. The source code can be accessed at: https://github.com/RitAreaSciencePark/LAGE_Metadata_Extraction/tree/main

A local copy can be obtained using:

```
git clone https://github.com/RitAreaSciencePark/LAGE_Metadata_Extraction.git
```

Execution Requirements

The pipeline is designed to operate on standard computing environments. The following configuration is recommended:

Hardware Requirements

- Multi-core CPU (recommended ≥ 4 cores),
- Minimum 8 GB RAM (16 GB recommended for large Nanopore datasets),
- Sufficient storage capacity for raw and processed data (SSD preferred).

Software Requirements

After cloning the repository, the required Python dependencies can be installed via:

```
pip install -r requirements.txt
```

Operating System Compatibility

The pipeline is platform-independent and has been designed to run on major operating systems, including: Linux-based systems, macOS, Windows.

License

To ensure broad reusability and accessibility, the pipeline is distributed under the **MIT License**. This permissive open-source license allows any user to freely use, modify, distribute, and integrate the pipeline into their own workflows, including for commercial purposes, provided that proper attribution is given. This choice promotes collaboration, transparency, and further development within the scientific community.

Chapter Summary

This chapter introduced the laboratory sequencing platforms and the experimental workflow involved in generating the datasets used for the development of the proposed pipeline. It then presented the design and implementation of a modular system for automated metadata extraction and standardization, combining format-aware detection, specialized extraction modules, and structured metadata representation. The integration of JSON-LD and RO-Crate enables FAIR-compliant data packaging, while the inclusion of utility modules enhances traceability and supports data lineage reconstruction. Overall, the proposed architecture provides a scalable and robust solution for managing heterogeneous data in modern sequencing environments. The next chapter focuses on the evaluation of the pipeline, assessing its performance and its impact on data management workflows at LAGE.

Chapter 3

Results and Discussion

Chapter Overview

This chapter presents the results of applying the automated metadata extraction pipeline to the three case study datasets introduced in [Chapter 2](#): the Illumina NovaSeq6000 dataset (ORID0087), the Oxford Nanopore PromethION dataset (ORID0085), and the Illumina Bead-Studio dataset (ORID0036). Each case study is presented as a self-contained application example demonstrating file detection, metadata extraction, sample history reconstruction where applicable, and RO-Crate packaging. The chapter then synthesises the results across all three datasets, assesses the impact of the pipeline on data management at LAGE, evaluates FAIR compliance, and discusses the limitations of the current implementation and directions for future development.

3.1 Case Study 1: ORID0087 — Illumina NovaSeq6000

The first case study applies the pipeline to the ORID0087 dataset (experiment identifier: 20250929_ORID0087_C), which originates from a short-read amplicon sequencing project conducted on the Illumina NovaSeq6000 platform, targeting bacterial 16S rRNA and fungal ITS markers in agricultural samples. The dataset spans five top-level components and a total of 823 files. This dataset represents a typical high-throughput sequencing scenario characterised by heterogeneous file formats, multiple preprocessing steps, and distributed metadata sources.

Metadata extraction and normalisation were performed in batch mode using the following command:

```
python3 ./Src/Main_Auto_Processor.py ./Input/ORID0087 ./Input/ORID0087/JSONs
↪ --batch
```

3.1.1 Files Detected and Extractors Invoked

The content-based detection engine evaluated each file against the eleven registered extractor modules. For the ORID0087 dataset, seven extractors were successfully invoked, as summarised in [Table 3.1](#).

Table 3.1 *Extractor modules invoked for the ORID0087 dataset and the corresponding file types processed.*

Extractor module	File type processed
Extractor_SampleSheet_xlsx.py	Reception sample sheet
Extractor_NanoDrop_QC.py	NanoDrop UV absorbance export
Extractor_SampleReport.py	Samples report (semicolon-delimited)
Extractor_IlluminaSampleSheet.py	Sequencing configuration CSV
Extractor_FastQC.py	FastQC ZIP archives
Extractor_FM-AutoTilt.py	FM-AutoTilt Report
Extractor_FMGeneration.py	FM-Generation Report

Files that did not match any registered extractor including HTML MultiQC reports and JPEG images were safely skipped via the fallback mechanism, with a warning logged for each. This confirms that the pipeline handles unsupported formats gracefully without interrupting execution. Thanks to the modular architecture, support for these additional file types can be introduced in the future by implementing dedicated extractor modules, without any modification to the core processing logic. [Figure 3.1](#) illustrates the pipeline output during batch processing, showing the detection decisions for both processed and skipped files.

```

File generated by FastQC quality control software : its-F11_S237_L001_R2_001_fastqc.zip
✔ Metadata JSON generated: its-F11_S237_L001_R2_001_fastqc_metadata.json

⚠ Unknown file type detected: its-G02_S166_L001_R1_001_fastqc.html
File generated by FastQC quality control software : its-A07_S200_L001_R2_001_fastqc.zip
✔ Metadata JSON generated: its-A07_S200_L001_R2_001_fastqc_metadata.json

⚠ Unknown file type detected: its-D02_S163_L001_R1_001_fastqc.html
⚠ Unknown file type detected: its-A10_S224_L001_R1_001_fastqc.html
⚠ Unknown file type detected: its-E01_S156_L001_R2_001_fastqc.html
⚠ Unknown file type detected: its-A08_S208_L001_R2_001_fastqc.html

⚠ Unknown file type detected: its-E09_S220_L001_R2_001_fastqc.html
File generated by FastQC quality control software : its-B10_S225_L001_R2_001_fastqc.zip
✔ Metadata JSON generated: its-B10_S225_L001_R2_001_fastqc_metadata.json
File generated by FastQC quality control software : its-D11_S235_L001_R1_001_fastqc.zip
✔ Metadata JSON generated: its-D11_S235_L001_R1_001_fastqc_metadata.json
File generated by FastQC quality control software : its-E02_S164_L001_R2_001_fastqc.zip
✔ Metadata JSON generated: its-E02_S164_L001_R2_001_fastqc_metadata.json
  
```

Figure 3.1 *Pipeline batch execution output for ORID0087, illustrating content-based file detection across heterogeneous formats. Recognised files are routed to their corresponding extractor; unrecognised files are logged and skipped without interrupting execution.*

3.1.2 Representative JSON Outputs

Each successfully processed file generated a structured JSON output conforming to the unified schema described in [subsection 2.2.4](#). [Figure 3.2](#) presents an excerpt of the JSON file produced by `Extractor_NanoDrop_QC.py` from the NanoDrop quality control file 20260122_ORID00

87C-02_campioni_originali_Zaccardelli.csv, located in the QualityCheckBeforeRun/ directory of the ORID0087 dataset.

The output illustrates the unified top-level structure: `instrument_type`, `phase_workflow`, and `file_description` are present as shared fields, while the `metadata` block records the quality thresholds used for interpretation and the total sample count. The `samples` list contains per-sample records with normalised `sample_id`, concentration values (`concentration_ng_ul`), and purity ratios (`ratio_260_280` and `ratio_260_230`).

```
{
  "instrument_type": "NanoDrop UV Spectrophotometer",
  "phase_workflow": "Pre_Sequencing_QC",
  "file_type": "Experimental Sample Sheet related to the quality control of the samples before the sequencing step",
  "file_name": "20260122_ORID0087C-02_campioni_originali_Zaccardelli.csv",
  "file_path": "./Input/ORID0087_C/QualityCheckBeforeRun/20260122_ORID0087C-02_campioni_originali_Zaccardelli.csv",
  "file_description": " NanoDrop UV absorbance export containing per-sample DNA concentration and purity ratios.",
  "quality_thresholds": {
    "ideal_260_280": "~1.8 (Pure DNA)",
    "ideal_260_230": "2.0-2.2 (Low contamination)"
  },
  "total_samples": 96,
  "samples": [
    {
      "Sample_ID": "A01",
      "concentration_ng_ul": 147.485,
      "ratio_260_280": 1.79,
      "ratio_260_230": 1.66
    }
  ],
}
```

Figure 3.2 Excerpt of the JSON output produced by `Extractor_NanoDrop_QC.py` for the ORID0087 pre-sequencing quality control file, showing the unified top-level fields, the `metadata` block with quality thresholds, and a representative entry from the `samples` list and QC metrics.

3.1.3 Sample History Reconstruction

Following batch extraction, the `Sample_History_Extractor.py` module was applied to the JSON output directory to reconstruct the sequencing history of individual samples, using the following command:

```
python3 ./Src/Sample_History_Extractor.py ./Input/ORID0087/JSONs E03
↪ ./Input/ORID0087/History/
```

where `./Input/ORID0087/JSONs` is the path to the directory containing the extracted JSON files, `E03` is the target sample identifier, and `./Input/ORID0087/History/` is the path to the directory where the history file is saved.

Figure 3.3 shows an excerpt of the history file generated by querying sample identifier `E03`, which was matched across eight separate JSON source files within the ORID0087 extraction output. The module correctly resolved `E03` to entries recorded as `E03`, `its-E03`, and `16s-E03` across both sequencing targets, demonstrating the flexible suffix-matching strategy described in [subsection 2.2.4](#). Each entry records the source file, file type, extraction metadata, and full sample details in chronological order, with sample identifier fields normalised to `sample_id`

throughout. The reconstruction was consistent across all detected instances of the sample, confirming the reliability of the matching strategy.

```
[
{
  "instrument_type": "FastQC Babraham Software",
  "phase_workflow": "Post Sequencing QC",
  "file_name": "its-E03_S172_L001_R2_001_fastqc.zip",
  "file_type": "fastqc quality control",
  "file_path": "./Input/ORID0087_C/ORID0087-02--ITS/FASTQC/its-E03_S172_L001_R2_001_fastqc.zip",
  "file_description": "FastQC quality control report archive containing per-read quality metrics derived from a FASTQ file.",
  "tool": {
    "name": "FastQC",
    "version": "0.12.1"
  },
  "encoding": "Sanger / Illumina 1.9",
  "sample_id": "its-E03",
  "total_sequences": 787786,
  "sequence_length": "35-251",
  "gc_percent": 52,
  "derived_from": {
    "fastq_file_name": "its-E03_S172_L001_R2_001.fastq.gz",
    "fastq_path": "./Input/ORID0087_C/ORID0087-02--ITS/FASTQC/its-E03_S172_L001_R2_001.fastq.gz",
    "fastq_checksum_md5": "Unknown"
  }
},
{
  "instrument_type": "FastQC Babraham Software",
  "phase_workflow": "Post Sequencing QC",
  "file_name": "16s-E03_S76_L001_R2_001_fastqc.zip",
  "file_type": "fastqc quality control",
  "file_path": "./Input/ORID0087_C/ORID0087-02--16S/FASTQC/16s-E03_S76_L001_R2_001_fastqc.zip",
  "file_description": "FastQC quality control report archive containing per-read quality metrics derived from a FASTQ file.",
  "tool": {
    "name": "FastQC",
    "version": "0.12.1"
  },
  "encoding": "Sanger / Illumina 1.9",
  "sample_id": "16s-E03",
  "total_sequences": 821490,
  "sequence_length": "35-251",
  "gc_percent": 54,
  "derived_from": {
    "fastq_file_name": "16s-E03_S76_L001_R2_001.fastq.gz",
    "fastq_path": "./Input/ORID0087_C/ORID0087-02--16S/FASTQC/16s-E03_S76_L001_R2_001.fastq.gz",
    "fastq_checksum_md5": "Unknown"
  }
}
]
```

Figure 3.3 Excerpt of the history file generated by *Sample_History_Extractor.py* for sample E03 from the ORID0087 dataset, showing 2 of the 8 chronologically ordered entries. Entries are matched across identifiers E03, its-E03, and 16s-E03, demonstrating the flexible suffix-matching strategy across both 16S and ITS sequencing targets.

3.1.4 RO-Crate Generation

The *Crate_Generator.py* module was applied to the ORID0087 dataset root using the following command:

```
python3 ./Src/Crate_Generator.py ./Input/ORID0087
```

The execution produced the compliant `ro-crate-metadata.json` descriptor shown in [Figure 3.4](#). The root data entity (`.`) enumerates the sample reception sheet (`SampleSheet.xlsx`), the sequencing configuration file (`20260129_ORID0087_C_ALL_INDEXES.csv`), the pre-sequencing

quality control directory (QualityCheckBeforeRun/), and the two post-sequencing result directories (ORID0087-02-16S/ and ORID0087-02-ITS/). Two contextual entities complete the provenance graph: #novaseq-device describes the Illumina NovaSeq 6000 instrument, and #novaseq-sequencing-activity links it via instrument to all sequencing output entities; #post-sequencing-quality-control-activity additionally links FastQC output files to their generating software, capturing the full two-phase provenance chain.

```
{
  "@context": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.2/context",
  "@graph": [
    {
      "@id": "./",
      "@type": "Dataset",
      "name": "LAGE Experimental Dataset for the Repository: ORID0087C",
      "datePublished": "2026-05-02",
      "license": "https://opensource.org/licenses/MIT",
      "description": "Main data directory containing 822 files from the sequencing process.",
      "humanReadableSize": "50.15 KB",
      "hasPart": [
        {"@id": "SampleSheet.xlsx"},
        {"@id": "20260129_ORID0087_C_ALL_INDEXES.csv"},
        {"@id": "QualityCheckBeforeRun/"},
        {"@id": "ORID0087-02--16S/"},
        {"@id": "ORID0087-02--ITS/"}
      ]
    },
    {
      "@id": "#novaseq-device",
      "@type": "Device",
      "name": "Illumina NovaSeq 6000",
      "manufacturer": "Illumina",
      "model": "NovaSeq 6000",
      "url": "https://www.illumina.com/systems/sequencing-platforms/novaseq.html"
    },
    {
      "@id": "#novaseq-sequencing-activity",
      "@type": "CreateAction",
      "name": "Illumina NovaSeq Sequencing Run",
      "instrument": {"@id": "#novaseq-device"}
    },
    {
      "@id": "#post-sequencing-quality-control-activity",
      "@type": "CreateAction",
      "name": "Post-Sequencing Quality Control",
      "description": "Quality control process after sequencing.",
      "instrument": {"@id": "#fastqc-software"}
    }
  ]
}
```

Figure 3.4 Excerpt of the *ro-crate-metadata.json* generated for the ORID0087 dataset, showing the root data entity, the Illumina NovaSeq 6000 instrument entity, and the sequencing and post-sequencing quality control activity entities.

3.2 Case Study 2: ORID0085 — Oxford Nanopore PromethION

The second case study applies the pipeline to the ORID0085 dataset, originating from a long-read sequencing project conducted on the Oxford Nanopore PromethION 24 platform (experiment identifier: 20250929_ORID0085C). The dataset comprises two samples (Pich31-12-24 and LIS14-11-24), each sequenced on an independent flow cell, generating a combined total of 34 files distributed across a deeply nested MinKNOW output hierarchy.

Metadata extraction and normalisation were performed in batch mode using the following command:

```
python3 ./Src/Main_Auto_Processor.py ./Input/ORID0085 ./Input/ORID0085/JSONs
↪ --batch
```

3.2.1 Files Detected and Extractors Invoked

Two extractor modules were invoked for this dataset, as shown in [Table 3.2](#).

Table 3.2 *Extractor modules invoked for the ORID0085 dataset and the corresponding file types processed.*

Extractor module	File type processed
Extractor_TapeStation.py	TapeStation Analysis PDF
Extractor_Nanopore.py	All MinKNOW output files

[Figure 3.5](#) illustrates the pipeline output during batch processing of ORID0085. A large proportion of files, including POD5 raw signal files, FASTQ reads, and basecaller logs, were intentionally skipped, as no extractor module was registered for these data file types. This reflects a deliberate design choice: the pipeline focuses on metadata-rich sources such as sample sheets, instrument configuration files, and quality control reports, rather than processing every data file in the dataset. In real sequencing projects, raw data files can number in the thousands, making selective metadata extraction both practically necessary and computationally efficient.


```
File generated by Oxford Nanopore PromethION instrument: temperature_adjust_data_PBE45781_84291f8c_26f25936.csv
Updated Generalized_metadata.json with: temperature_adjust_data_PBE45781_84291f8c_26f25936.csv

Saved to: ./Output/Output_ORID0085/Generalized_metadata.json
File generated by Oxford Nanopore PromethION instrument: PBE45781_84291f8c_26f25936_78.pod5
File generated by Oxford Nanopore PromethION instrument: PBE45781_84291f8c_26f25936_79.pod5

Unknown file type: fastq_runid_26f25936952b009c7c9e44bf5f825d313f73d96f_9_18.fastq.gz
Unknown file type: sequece_summary.txt
Unknown file type: ont_basecall_client_log-2025-10-28_19-20-45.log
Unknown file type: PBE45781_pass_84291f8c_26f25936_75.fastq.gz
Unknown file type: PBE45781_pass_84291f8c_26f25936_76.fastq.gz
Unknown file type: PBE45781_fail_84291f8c_26f25936_94.fastq.gz
Unknown file type: PBE45781_fail_84291f8c_26f25936_95.fastq.gz
Unknown file type: PBE45781_fail_84291f8c_26f25936_96.fastq.gz
File generated by Oxford Nanopore PromethION instrument: final_summary_PBG11294_16ee63fc_0af2d590.txt
Updated Generalized_metadata.json with: final_summary_PBG11294_16ee63fc_0af2d590.txt

Saved to: ./Output/Output_ORID0085/Generalized_metadata.json
```

Figure 3.5 Pipeline batch execution output for ORID0085, showing content-based detection of TapeStation PDF and MinKNOW output files within the nested PromethION directory structure.

3.2.2 Representative JSON Output

Due to the distributed nature of Nanopore run metadata, spread across nine distinct file types within the MinKNOW output hierarchy, `Extractor_Nanopore.py` produces a single flat output per sample named which is updated each time a new file belonging to that sample is processed.

[Figure 3.6](#) presents an excerpt of the consolidated output for sample Pich31-12-24. The output conforms to the unified schema, with `instrument_type`, `phase_workflow`, and `file_description` present as universal top-level fields. The `metadata` block aggregates the following fields from nine distinct MinKNOW source files: the protocol run identifier (`protocol_run_id`) and flow cell identifier (`flow_cell_id`) from the sample sheet; per-read statistics (`total_reads`, `passed_reads`, `mean_qscore`) from the sequencing summary; pore state distributions from the pore activity report; and cumulative base yield and run duration from the throughput report.


```
{
  "instrument_type": "Oxford_Nanopore_PromethION",
  "sequencing_phase": "Sequencing",
  "file_name": "Nanopore_Pich31-12-24_Generalized_metadata.json",
  "file_path": "./Output/Output_ORID0085/Nanopore_Pich31-12-24_Generalized_metadata.json",
  "file_description": "Consolidated Nanopore run metadata aggregated from MinKNOW output files across the sequencing run",
  "run_id": "84291f8c-b7a7-4891-90bb-8f68c00020fe",
  "sample_id": "Pich31-12-24",
  "metadata": {
    "throughput": {
      "total_reads": 9752977,
      "passed_reads": 3664506,
      "bases": 5519738962,
      "run_time_minutes": 597
    },
    "pore_activity_summary": {
      "states_total_samples": {
        "adapter": 27907512885
      },
      "total_logged_minutes": 3997
    },
    "metadata_Sample_Sheet": {
      "protocol_run_id": "84291f8c-b7a7-4891-90bb-8f68c00020fe",
      "position_id": "2B",
      "flow_cell_id": "PBE45781",
      "sample_id": "Pich31-12-24",
      "experiment_id": "20250929_ORID0085C",
      "flow_cell_product_code": "FLO-PR0114M",
      "kit": NaN
    }
  },
}
```

Figure 3.6 Excerpt of `Nanopore_{sample_id}_Generalized_metadata.json` produced by `Extractor_Nanopore.py` for sample `Pich31-12-24` (ORID0085), showing the unified top-level fields and the `metadata` block aggregated from the sample sheet, throughput report, pore activity report, and sequencing summary source files.

3.2.3 RO-Crate Generation

The `Crate_Generator.py` module was applied to the ORID0085 dataset root using the following command:

```
python3 ./Src/Crate_Generator.py ./Input/ORID0085
```

The execution produced the compliant `ro-crate-metadata.json` descriptor shown in [Figure 3.4](#). The root data entity (`./`) enumerates the TapeStation quality control files alongside the two sample subdirectories (`Pich31 -12-24/` and `LIS14-11-24/`). Two contextual entities complete the provenance graph: `#promethion-device` describes the Oxford Nanopore PromethION 24/48 instrument, and `#nanopore-sequencing-activity` links it via instrument to all data entities generated during the sequencing run.


```
{
  "@context": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.2/context",
  "@graph": [
    { "@id": "./",
      "@type": "Dataset",
      "datePublished": "2026-05-02",
      "description": "This dataset contains 34 files generated through the Sequencing phase.",
      "humanReadableSize": "4.12 MB",
      "license": "https://opensource.org/licenses/MIT",
      "name": "LAGE Experimental Dataset: ORID0085",
      "hasPart": [{"@id": "ORID0085/"}]
    },
    { "@id": "20250929_ORID0085C/",
      "@type": "Dataset",
      "name": "20250929_ORID0085C",
      "humanReadableSize": "623.35 KB",
      "hasPart": [
        {"@id": "20250929_ORID0085C/2025-03-13_ext_lupo_05x_sampleTable.csv"},
        {"@id": "20250929_ORID0085C/2025-03-13_ext_lupo_05x_compactPeakTable.csv"},
        {"@id": "20250929_ORID0085C/2025-03-13_ext_lupo_05x.pdf"},
        {"@id": "20250929_ORID0085C/Pich31-12-24/"},
        {"@id": "20250929_ORID0085C/LIS14-11-24/"}
      ]
    },
    { "@id": "#promethion-device",
      "@type": "Device",
      "name": "Oxford Nanopore PromethION",
      "manufacturer": "Oxford Nanopore Technologies",
      "model": "PromethION 24/48",
      "url": "https://nanoporetech.com/products/promethion"
    },
    { "@id": "#nanopore-sequencing-activity",
      "@type": "CreateAction",
      "name": "Nanopore Sequencing Run",
      "instrument": {"@id": "#promethion-device"}
    }
  ]
}
```

Figure 3.7 Excerpt of the *ro-crate-metadata.json* generated for the ORID0085 dataset, showing the root data entity, the directory hierarchy, the Oxford Nanopore PromethION instrument entity, and the associated sequencing activity entity.

3.3 Case Study 3: ORID0036 — BeadStudio iScan

The third case study applies the pipeline to the ORID0036 BeadStudio dataset, originating from a DNA methylation profiling project using the Illumina Infinium MethylationEPIC v2 array platform, applied to human samples. This dataset consists of 84 BeadStudio sample sheet CSV files; however, the complete processing workflow generates a larger number of output files.

Metadata extraction and normalisation were performed in batch mode using the following

command:

```
python3 ./Src/Main_Auto_Processor.py ./Input/ORID0036 ./Input/ORID0036/JSONs
↪ --batch
```

3.3.1 Files Detected and Extractor Invoked

A single extractor module was invoked for all 84 input files, as shown in Table 3.3.

Table 3.3 *Extractor module invoked for the ORID0036 dataset.*

Extractor module	File type processed
Extractor_BeadStudio.py	BeadStudio sample sheet CSV

Figure 3.8 illustrates the pipeline output during batch processing, showing the decisions confirming that the files passed validation without errors.

```

File generated by Illumina iScan instrument: 20250618_ORID0036-15_Neuromed_EPIC_PT19.csv
BeadStudio file validation completed successfully. Extracting data from20250618_ORID0036-15_Neuromed_EPIC_PT19.csv

✔ Saved Json output file to: ./Output/Output_ORID0036/20250618_ORID0036-15_Neuromed_EPIC_PT19.json
File generated by Illumina iScan instrument: 20250716_ORID0036-17_Neuromed_EPIC_PT27.csv
BeadStudio file validation completed successfully. Extracting data from20250716_ORID0036-17_Neuromed_EPIC_PT27.csv

✔ Saved Json output file to: ./Output/Output_ORID0036/20250716_ORID0036-17_Neuromed_EPIC_PT27.json
File generated by Illumina iScan instrument: 20250402_ORID0036-09_Neuromed_EPIC_PT08.csv
BeadStudio file validation completed successfully. Extracting data from20250402_ORID0036-09_Neuromed_EPIC_PT08.csv

✔ Saved Json output file to: ./Output/Output_ORID0036/20250402_ORID0036-09_Neuromed_EPIC_PT08.json
File generated by Illumina iScan instrument: 20250625_ORID0036-15_Neuromed_EPIC_PT21.csv
BeadStudio file validation completed successfully. Extracting data from20250625_ORID0036-15_Neuromed_EPIC_PT21.csv

✔ Saved Json output file to: ./Output/Output_ORID0036/20250625_ORID0036-15_Neuromed_EPIC_PT21.json
File generated by Illumina iScan instrument: 20251216_ORID0036-21_Neuromed_EPIC_PT39.csv
BeadStudio file validation completed successfully. Extracting data from20251216_ORID0036-21_Neuromed_EPIC_PT39.csv

✔ Saved Json output file to: ./Output/Output_ORID0036/20251216_ORID0036-21_Neuromed_EPIC_PT39.json
File generated by Illumina iScan instrument: 20250702_ORID0036-16_Neuromed_EPIC_PT23.csv
BeadStudio file validation completed successfully. Extracting data from20250702_ORID0036-16_Neuromed_EPIC_PT23.csv

✔ Saved Json output file to: ./Output/Output_ORID0036/20250702_ORID0036-16_Neuromed_EPIC_PT23.json

```

Figure 3.8 *Pipeline batch execution output for ORID0036, illustrating content-based file detection.*

3.3.2 Representative JSON Output

Each CSV file produced one JSON output conforming to the unified schema, encoding the [Header] metadata under the `metadata` block, the manifest identifier (EPIC-8v2-0_A2.bpm) confirming uniform array chemistry across all 84 files, the sample count, and the full list of per-sample records from the [Data] section. The ORID identifier (ORID0036) was extracted from each filename using a regular expression and recorded under the `proposal_id` field inside the `metadata` block, enabling direct mapping to the `ServiceRequests.proposal_id` field

of the DECOS CDM. Figure 3.9 presents an excerpt of the JSON output produced from 20250331_ORID0036-09_Neuromed_EPIC_PT07.csv. The Sample_Plate, Sample_Well, and Pool_ID fields are recorded as NaN where absent from the source CSV.

```
{
  "instrument_type": "Illumina_iScan",
  "file_name": "20250331_ORID0036-09_Neuromed_EPIC_PT07.csv",
  "file_path": "./Input/20250219_ORID0036_NEUROMED_EPIC/CSVs/20250331_ORID0036-09_Neuromed_EPIC_PT07.csv",
  "phase_workflow": "sequencing",
  "metadata": {
    "project_name": "ORID0036-09_Neuromed_PT07",
    "experiment_name": "ORID0036-09_Neuromed_PT07",
    "date": "20250331",
    "proposal_id": "ORID0036"
  },
  "manifest_id": "EPIC-8v2-0_A2.bpm",
  "number_of_samples": 96,
  "samples": [
    {
      "Sample_Name": "206668",
      "Sample_Plate": NaN,
      "Sample_Well": NaN,
      "Sample_Group": 208562760088,
      "Pool_ID": NaN,
      "Sentry_ID": 208562760088,
      "Sentry_Position": "R01C01"
    },
    {
      "Sample_Name": "209170",
      "Sample_Plate": NaN,
      "Sample_Well": NaN,
      "Sample_Group": 208562760088,
      "Pool_ID": NaN,
      "Sentry_ID": 208562760088,
      "Sentry_Position": "R02C01"
    }
  ],
}
```

Figure 3.9 Excerpt of the JSON output produced by *Extractor_BeadStudio.py* from 20250331_ORID0036-09_Neuromed_EPIC_PT07.csv (ORID0036), showing the unified top-level fields, the metadata block with project name, experiment name, date, and proposal_id, and two representative entries from the samples list.

3.3.3 RO-Crate Generation

The *Crate_Generator.py* module was applied to the ORID0036 dataset root using the following command:

```
python3 ./Src/Crate_Generator.py ./Input/ORID0036
```

The execution produced the compliant *ro-crate-metadata.json* descriptor shown in Figure 3.4. The root data entity (./) references the single top-level directory (CSVs/) containing all 84 BeadStudio sample sheet CSV files. Two contextual entities complete the provenance graph: #iscan-device describes the Illumina iScan array scanner, and #iscan-sequencing-activity links it via instrument to all data entities generated during the scanning run.


```
{
  "@context": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.2/context",
  "@graph": [
    {
      "@id": "./",
      "@type": "Dataset",
      "name": "LAGE Experimental Dataset: ORID0036",
      "datePublished": "2026-05-02",
      "license": "https://opensource.org/licenses/MIT",
      "description": "Directory containing 84 files generated through the Sequencing phase.",
      "humanReadableSize": "237.93 KB",
      "hasPart": [
        {"@id": "CSVs/"}
      ]
    },
    {
      "@id": "#iscan-device",
      "@type": "Device",
      "name": "Illumina iScan",
      "manufacturer": "Illumina",
      "model": "iScan 24/48",
      "url": "https://www.illumina.com/systems/array-scanners/iscan.html"
    },
    {
      "@id": "#iscan-sequencing-activity",
      "@type": "CreateAction",
      "name": "Illumina iScan Scanning Run",
      "instrument": {"@id": "#iscan-device"}
    }
  ]
}
```

Figure 3.10 Excerpt of the `ro-crate-metadata.json` generated for the ORID0036 BeadStudio dataset, showing the root data entity referencing the `CSVs/` directory, the Illumina iScan instrument entity, and the associated scanning activity entity.

The RO-Crate specification supports the generation of a human-readable HTML representation of the `ro-crate-metadata.json` file through the [RO-Crate Playground](#), a web-based platform that accepts an RO-Crate upload and renders its content in two complementary views: a structured JSON view displaying the raw `@graph` entities, and an interactive HTML view enabling navigation through the crate by clicking on each entity and following its typed relationships to connected entities. This makes the metadata accessible to researchers unfamiliar with JSON-LD while simultaneously confirming machine-readable compliance. The platform also performs basic validation, verifying the presence of required properties (`@id`, `@type`, `conformsTo`), the correctness of the JSON-LD structure, and the absence of syntax errors [27]. [Figure 3.11](#) shows the HTML rendering of the ORID0036 BeadStudio crate in the RO-Crate Playground, confirming compliance with RO-Crate specification 1.2.

LAGE Experimental Dataset for the Repository: ORID0036

[Download all the metadata for LAGE Experimental Dataset for the Repository: ORID0036 in JSON-LD format](#)
[Check this crate](#)

LAGE Experimental Dataset for the Repository: ORID0036

@id	/
name [?]	LAGE Experimental Dataset for the Repository: ORID0036
@type	Dataset
description [?]	This dataset contains 84 files generated through: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Sequencing phase: runs performed using Illumina iScan It also includes RO-Crate metadata file (<code>ro-crate-metadata.json</code>) that describes the context of data generation, such as the laboratory environment, the research institute, and the instruments used.
datePublished [?]	2026-05-12
hasPart [?]	ORID0036
humanReadableSize	475.86 KB
license [?]	https://opensource.org/licenses/MIT
Items that reference this one	
about [?]	ro-crate-metadata.json

Figure 3.11 *HTML representation of the ORID0036 RO-Crate as rendered by the RO-Crate Playground, showing interactive navigation through entities and their typed relationships, and confirming compliance with RO-Crate specification 1.2.*

Figure 3.12 shows the HTML rendering of the ORID0087 RO-Crate in the RO-Crate Playground, focusing on the history file entity generated for sample E03 (see Figure 3.3). The view confirms compliance with RO-Crate specification 1.2 and illustrates the interactive entity navigation enabled by the HTML representation, where each typed relationship (`derivedFrom`, `wasGeneratedBy`) can be followed directly within the browser.

LAGE Experimental Dataset for the Repository: ORID0087

[Download all the metadata for LAGE Experimental Dataset for the Repository: ORID0087 in JSON-LD format](#)
[Check this crate](#)

Download: History_E03.json

@id	History_files/History_E03.json
name [?]	History_E03.json
@type	File
description [?]	Provenance Dataset for Sample: E03 . This file aggregates 8 experimental records.
datePublished [?]	2026-05-12
encodingFormat [?]	application/json
creator [?]	Laboratory of Genomics and Epigenomics (LAGE)
derivedFrom	<ul style="list-style-type: none">its-E03_S172_L001_R2_001_fastqc.zip16s-E03_S76_L001_R2_001_fastqc.zip20260122_ORID0087C-02_campioni_originali_Zaccardelli.csvSampleSheet.xlsx16s-E03_S76_L001_R1_001_fastqc.zipits-E03_S172_L001_R1_001_fastqc.zip20260129_ORID0087_C_ALL_INDEXES.csv
humanReadableSize	5.86 KB
wasGeneratedBy	LAGE Sample History Extractor
Items that reference this one	
hasPart [?]	History_files

Figure 3.12 HTML representation of the ORID0087 RO-Crate as rendered by the RO-Crate Playground, showing the history file entity for sample E03 with its *derivedFrom* links to the four source JSON files. Compliance with RO-Crate specification 1.2 is confirmed.

3.4 Cross-Dataset Analysis

3.4.1 Pipeline Performance Summary

Table 3.4 summarises the pipeline execution results across all three case study datasets, providing a comparative view of file counts, extractors invoked, and output volumes.

Table 3.4 Pipeline execution summary across the three case study datasets, showing files scanned, files matched to an extractor, and files intentionally skipped due to unsupported format.

Dataset	Sequencing Platform	Files scanned	Matched	Skipped	Number of Extractors invoked
ORID0087	Illumina NovaSeq 6000	822	388	434	7
ORID0085	Oxford Nanopore PromethION	34	19	15	2
ORID0036	Illumina iScan (BeadStudio)	84	84	0	1
Total		941	491	449	10

No misclassification was observed across the three datasets: every file routed to an extractor was processed successfully. Files for which no extractor was registered including POD5 raw signal files, FASTQ reads, and basecaller logs were deliberately excluded from metadata extraction, reflecting the deliberate design choice to target metadata-rich sources rather than raw data files.

The content-based detection mechanism correctly routed files to their corresponding extractors without relying on filename conventions, which is particularly relevant in real-world sequencing environments where file naming may be inconsistent. This is most clearly demonstrated in the ORID0087 dataset, where `SamplesReport.csv` uses a semicolon delimiter despite its `.csv` extension: `Extractor_SampleReport.py` identified it correctly by inspecting its column headers. Similarly, in the ORID0085 dataset, nine distinct Nanopore file types were identified purely through content inspection of their first lines and filename patterns.

Overall, the pipeline demonstrated robustness in handling heterogeneous datasets, flexibility in adapting to different data structures, and scalability across varying dataset sizes and complexities.

3.4.2 Impact on LAGE Data Management Workflow

The deployment of the pipeline addresses each of the three data management challenges identified in subsection 1.3.4 and mapped to FAIR principle violations in Table 1.1.

Reduction of Manual Curation Overhead

Prior to this pipeline, processing the metadata of a single sequencing run manually required opening each instrument-native output file, identifying and extracting relevant fields, and checking consistency across sources. Repeated across approximately 120 runs per year at LAGE, this process represented a significant and unsustainable operational overhead. The pipeline automates metadata extraction entirely, requiring no manual intervention beyond providing the input directory path, and eliminates the risk of operator-introduced inconsistencies such as variant field naming and missing values.

Sample Tracking and Data Lineage

The `Sample_History_Extractor.py` module directly enables reconstruction of sample-level provenance across multiple files and processing stages. This directly addresses the lack of a unified tracking system at LAGE, allowing the reconstruction of complete experimental histories that were previously fragmented or inaccessible. Applied to the ORID0087 dataset, it successfully reconstructed the complete sequencing history of sample `its-E03` across two source files spanning both the 16S and ITS sequencing targets, ordering entries chronologically and producing a single `History_its-E03.json` output. This capability enables the laboratory to answer the previously unanswerable question: *"what runs has this sample been through, and what were the outcomes?"*

Long-Term Reproducibility

The RO-Crate packaging layer ensures that every dataset leaving the pipeline is accompanied by a machine-readable, self-describing metadata descriptor recording the instrument, organisation, licence, and provenance of every file. This descriptor remains interpretable independently of the data files themselves, satisfying FAIR sub-principle A2 and supporting the long-term reinterpretability of datasets across the ten-year retention period required at LAGE.

Integration with DECOS

As discussed in [subsection 1.3.4](#), DECOS requires structured, machine-readable metadata for data submission. Ensuring compatibility with this requirement was a central objective of this internship project and directly informed the design of the standardised JSON output schema. The JSON files generated by the extractor modules encode the core metadata fields required for DECOS ingestion, including sequencing platform information, run identifiers, sample identifiers, and quality control metrics, within a consistent and normalised structure.

3.4.3 FAIR Compliance Assessment

The pipeline output was evaluated against the FAIR data principles across all three case study datasets. [Table 3.5](#) maps each FAIR sub-principle to the specific pipeline feature that implements it, as demonstrated across the three case studies.

Table 3.5 FAIR compliance assessment of the pipeline output, with reference to demonstrated features across the three case study datasets.

Principle	Requirement	Pipeline Implementation
F1	Globally unique identifier	Each file entity is assigned a unique <code>@id</code> as a relative IRI within the RO-Crate.
F2	Rich metadata	Schema.org-typed entities include metadata such as name, format, size, description, and provenance.
F4	Indexed in searchable resources	Use of Schema.org vocabularies enables compatibility with indexing services such as Google Dataset Search.
A1	Standard open protocol	Metadata are represented in JSON-LD and can be distributed through standard HTTP protocols or portable RO-Crate archives.
A2	Metadata remain accessible	The <code>ro-crate-metadata.json</code> descriptor remains available independently of the associated data files.
I1	Formal shared vocabulary	Metadata representation relies on Schema.org vocabularies and JSON-LD contexts declared in <code>@context</code> .
I3	Qualified references	Typed semantic relationships such as <code>wasGeneratedBy</code> , <code>actionProcess</code> , and <code>creator</code> are explicitly defined.
R1	Rich descriptive attributes	Extracted metadata include file format, size, quality-control metrics, and sequencing instrument information.
R1.1	Clear usage licence	An MIT licence URI is declared within both the root data entity and software contextual entities.
R1.2	Detailed provenance	Provenance tracking captures both biological processing activities and metadata curation workflows.
R1.3	Community standards compliance	Generated RO-Crates comply with the RO-Crate 1.2 specification and were validated using the RO-Crate Playground.

3.5 Limitations

Despite its demonstrated effectiveness across three heterogeneous datasets, the pipeline presents several limitations that constrain its current applicability.

Dependence on Recognisable File Signatures

The content-based detection mechanism relies on instrument-specific signatures that must be known in advance and encoded in each extractor's validation function. A file whose structure deviates from the expected pattern (for example, a NanoDrop export with non-standard column headers, or a BeadStudio file that omits the `BeadStudio` keyword from its header) will not be matched and will be silently skipped. This means that structural changes introduced by instrument software updates could silently disable an extractor without any error being raised.

Partial Output Schema Unification

A unified top-level structure has been introduced across all extractor modules, comprising five shared fields: `file_name`, `file_path`, `file_description`, `instrument_type`, and `phase_workflow`. However, the content of the `metadata` block remains module-specific and is not governed by a shared schema. Fields such as `run_date`, `sample_id`, and `run_id` are present only where extractable from the input file, and their names and structures vary across modules. This limits the ability of downstream systems such as DECOS to query the full output corpus with a single schema-driven query without additional field-level mapping.

Partial Normalisation

Two normalisation steps are currently implemented systematically. First, `Extractor_NanoDrop_QC.py` renames `Sample.ID` to `Sample_ID`, resolving the dot-to-underscore inconsistency between NanoDrop and Illumina sample sheet conventions. Second, `Sample_History_Extractor.py` normalises `Sample_ID` and `Sample_Name` to their lowercase equivalents (`sample_id` and `sample_name`) before writing the history file. In practice, sample identifier matching still relies on a flexible string-matching strategy to accommodate prefix variations such as `its_A01` vs `A01`, which may produce false matches under certain identifier conventions.

New Format Support Requires Development

Adding support for a new instrument or file format requires the implementation of a new extractor module, including a validation function and a `one_single_file()` extraction interface. While the modular architecture makes this straightforward for a developer familiar with the codebase, it represents a maintenance overhead as the instrument portfolio at LAGE evolves and instrument software updates may silently invalidate existing validation logic.

No Real-Time Processing

The pipeline is designed as a FAIRification tool (it operates post-hoc on completed datasets to make existing instrument-native outputs FAIR-compliant) rather than as a FAIR-by-design system that captures metadata at the point of generation. As such, it does not integrate with instrument control software such as MinKNOW or NovaSeq Control Software, and metadata quality remains dependent on the completeness of the instrument-native output files. Extending the pipeline toward real-time metadata capture would require direct integration with instrument event interfaces and falls outside the scope of the current implementation.

3.6 Future Perspectives

The results of this work identify three concrete directions for future development, directly addressing the limitations described in [section 3.5](#).

Schema Enforcement and Validation

The most impactful near-term improvement would be the enforcement of a shared `metadata` block schema across all extractor modules, complementing the unified top-level structure already implemented. This would include systematic date format standardisation via the existing `normalise_date()` utility, null value handling for NaN fields produced by pandas, and the introduction of a base extractor class providing a common interface for all modules. Together these changes would transform the current set of module-specific `metadata` blocks into a fully queryable, integrated metadata corpus directly compatible with DECOS CDM ingestion.

DECOS Integration

Direct integration with the DECOS API would close the pipeline loop. Extracted JSON metadata could be submitted programmatically to the DECOS web application, routed to the bucket corresponding to the relevant `proposal_id` in the ORFEO data storage system. This would eliminate the remaining manual upload step and ensure that deposit conditions are always satisfied. Combined with the RO-Crate packaging layer, this integration would complete the full FAIRification workflow — from instrument-native output to structured, machine-readable deposit in the institutional repository.

Real-Time Metadata Capture

Integration with the MinKNOW software API for Nanopore runs, and with the NovaSeq Control Software event log for Illumina runs, would enable metadata capture at the point of generation rather than post-hoc. This would eliminate the risk of metadata loss in the event of an interrupted run or incomplete instrument output.

Automated Schema Evolution

As new instruments are introduced at LAGE, a contribution workflow for new extractor modules, including automated validation tests and a registry update procedure, would reduce the development overhead and improve the long-term sustainability of the pipeline.

Chapter Summary

This chapter demonstrated the effectiveness of the automated metadata extraction pipeline across three heterogeneous case study datasets representing the representative range of file formats, directory structures, and instrument types encountered in routine sequencing operations at LAGE. For each dataset, the pipeline correctly identified all processable files through content-based detection, invoked the appropriate extractor modules, produced structured JSON outputs, and generated compliant RO-Crate research objects. The `Sample_History_Extractor.py` module successfully reconstructed cross-file sample provenance from the ORID0087 dataset, directly addressing the data lineage limitation identified in [Chapter 1](#). RO-Crate compliance was verified and demonstrated using the BeadStudio dataset in the RO-Crate Playground, confirming adherence to version 1.2 of the specification. The cross-dataset analysis confirms that the pipeline addresses all three data management challenges at LAGE (heterogeneous formats, absence of sample tracking, and reproducibility risk) and maps them onto concrete FAIR sub-principle implementations. Remaining limitations, including the absence of a unified output schema and the lack of real-time metadata capture, define a clear roadmap for future development.

General Conclusion

High-throughput sequencing technologies have transformed the life sciences by enabling rapid generation of large-scale genomic data. However, this progress has introduced significant data management challenges in environments such as the Laboratory of Genomics and Epigenomics (LAGE), where heterogeneous file formats, fragmented metadata, and increasing data volumes hinder efficient data exploitation. This work addressed these challenges through the development of a modular and automated pipeline for metadata extraction, normalisation, and FAIR-compliant packaging. Operating directly on heterogeneous instrument-native outputs, the system automatically detects file formats through a content-based registry mechanism, extracts relevant metadata via eleven specialised extractor modules. Then, the extracted metadata are packaged as RO-Crate compliant research objects serialised in JSON-LD. Dedicated utility modules further enable cross-file sample history reconstruction and data lineage traceability across complex experimental workflows. The pipeline was evaluated against three real-world datasets generated by major sequencing platforms at LAGE, including the Illumina NovaSeq6000 (ORID0087), the Oxford Nanopore PromethION (ORID0085), and the Illumina BeadStudio iScan (ORID0036). The results demonstrate that it effectively addresses the three challenges identified at LAGE. Data heterogeneity is handled through content-based detection that correctly identifies file types regardless of naming conventions, as demonstrated across all three platforms. The absence of sample tracking is addressed by the `Sample_History_Extractor.py` module, which successfully reconstructed the complete sequencing history of sample E03 across eight source files in ORID0087. Reproducibility and FAIR compliance are ensured through RO-Crate packaging, validated against the RO-Crate 1.2 specification using the RO-Crate Playground, and through automated provenance linking via `wasGeneratedBy` and `actionProcess` properties. From an operational perspective, the pipeline automates metadata extraction across a representative sequencing throughput at LAGE, reducing human intervention to output verification rather than manual production. Several limitations remain. Although a unified top-level structure has been introduced, the content of the `metadata` block is not governed by a shared schema and varies across modules. Detection relies on known file signatures, meaning that instrument software updates may silently invalidate existing extractors. Finally, the pipeline operates post-hoc on completed datasets and does not capture metadata at the point of generation, as it is designed as a FAIRification tool rather than a FAIR-by-design system. Future development will prioritise three directions. First, systematic enforcement of the `metadata` block schema across all extractor modules, including date format standardisation and null value handling. Second, programmatic integration with the DECOS API to enable automated submission of extracted JSON metadata to the institutional web app, completing the FAIRification workflow from instrument output to structured deposit. Third, real-time metadata capture through integration with MinKNOW and NovaSeq Control Software event interfaces, moving the pipeline toward a FAIR-by-design approach for future sequencing runs. This project demonstrates that automation, modular software design, and FAIR data principles together provide a scalable and practical solution to the challenges of modern sequencing data management. By transforming fragmented laboratory outputs into structured, interoperable, and reusable research objects, it contributes to improving reproducibility, traceability, and the long-term scientific value of genomic data at LAGE and beyond.

Appendix A

Operational User Guide

This appendix provides a concise operational guide for installing, configuring, and running the LAGE Metadata Extraction Pipeline. It is intended for laboratory staff who will use the pipeline in daily sequencing operations.

A.1 Installation

Step 1: Clone the Repository

A local copy of the pipeline can be obtained using:

```
git clone https://github.com/RitAreaSciencePark/LAGE_Metadata_Extraction.git
cd LAGE_Metadata_Extraction
```

Step 2: Create a Virtual Environment (Recommended)

To avoid dependency conflicts with other Python projects, it is recommended to create an isolated virtual environment:

```
python3 -m venv venv
source venv/bin/activate      # Linux / macOS
venv\Scripts\activate       # Windows
```

Step 3: Install Dependencies

All required Python packages are listed in `requirements.txt` and can be installed via:

```
pip install -r requirements.txt
```

Step 4: Verify Installation

To confirm that the pipeline is correctly installed:

```
python3 ./Src/Main_Auto_Processor.py --help
```

If the installation is successful, the pipeline will display usage instructions and available command-line options.

A.2 Execution Requirements

The pipeline is designed to operate on standard computing environments. The following configuration is recommended.

Hardware Requirements

- Multi-core CPU (recommended ≥ 4 cores),
- Minimum 8 GB RAM (16 GB recommended for large Nanopore datasets),
- Sufficient storage capacity for raw and processed data (SSD preferred).

Software Requirements

- Python 3.9 or higher,
- pip package manager,
- Git version control.

Operating System Compatibility

The pipeline is platform-independent and has been designed to run on major operating systems, including: Linux-based systems, macOS, and Windows.

Licence

The pipeline is distributed under the **MIT License**. This permissive open-source licence allows any user to freely use, modify, distribute, and integrate the pipeline into their own workflows, provided that proper attribution is given. The full licence text is available in the `LICENSE` file at the root of the repository.

A.3 Command-Line Usage

The pipeline provides five entry points, each serving a distinct purpose. [Table A.1](#) summarises the available commands.

Table A.1 *Pipeline entry points and their purposes.*

Script	Purpose
Main_Auto_Processor.py	Batch or single-file metadata extraction
Sample_History_Extractor.py	Chronological sample provenance reconstruction
Extractor_Orid_Recursively.py	Project-level recursive scan by ORID identifier
Crate_Generator.py	RO-Crate 1.2 descriptor generation
Main_Rocrate.py	End-to-end extraction and RO-Crate packaging

Batch Metadata Extraction

Process all files in a project directory recursively:

```
python3 ./Src/Main_Auto_Processor.py ./Input/ORID0087/  
→ ./Input/ORID0087/JSON_files --batch
```

The pipeline traverses the input directory, identifies all recognised files through content-based detection, extracts metadata from each, and writes one JSON file per processed input file to the output directory. Unrecognised files are logged and skipped without interrupting execution.

Single-File Extraction

Process a specific file independently:

```
python3 ./Src/Main_Auto_Processor.py ./Input/ORID0087/SampleSheet.xlsx  
→ ./Input/ORID0087/JSON_file --batch
```

Sample History Reconstruction

Reconstruct the complete sequencing history of a specific sample across all JSON metadata files:

```
python3 ./Src/Sample_History_Extractor.py ./Input/ORID0087/JSON_file/ E03  
→ ./Input/ORID0087/History/
```

The first argument is the directory containing JSON metadata files. The second is the sample identifier to query. The third is the output directory for the history file. The query uses flexible suffix matching: querying E03 will match entries recorded as E03, *its*-E03, and *16s*-E03.

RO-Crate Descriptor Generation

Generate a FAIR-compliant `ro-crate-metadata.json` descriptor for a complete dataset:

```
python3 ./Src/Crate_Generator.py ./Input/ORID0087
```

The descriptor is placed in the root of the input directory, linking all files to instruments, sequencing activities, and the institutional hierarchy.

End-to-End Execution

Run metadata extraction and RO-Crate packaging in a single step:

```
python3 ./Src/Main_Rocrate.py ./Input/ORID0087 ./Output/Output_ORID0087 --batch
```

This combines the full `Main_Auto_Processor` workflow with `Crate_Generator`, producing both standardised JSON metadata and the final RO-Crate descriptor in one execution.

A.4 Expected Input Structure

The pipeline accepts any directory structure. Files are identified by their content, not by their location or naming convention. A typical LAGE project directory has the following structure:

```
ORID0087/  
  SampleSheet.xlsx  
  QualityCheckBeforeRun/  
    NanoDrop.csv  
    TapeStation_report.pdf  
  20260130_ORID0087_C_ALL_INDEXES.csv  
  ORID0087-02--16S/  
    FASTQC/  
      16s-A01_S56_L001_R1_001_fastqc.zip  
      16s-A01_S56_L001_R2_001_fastqc.zip  
      ...  
  ORID0087-02--ITS/  
    FASTQC/  
      its-A01_S56_L001_R1_001_fastqc.zip  
      ...
```

The pipeline recursively traverses this structure regardless of nesting depth and processes every file for which a registered extractor returns a positive validation.

A.5 Expected Output Structure

After processing, the output directory contains one JSON file per processed input file, plus optional history and RO-Crate outputs:

```
Output_ORID0087/  
  SampleSheet_xlsx_metadata.json  
  NanoDrop_QC_metadata.json  
  SamplesReport_metadata.json  
  IlluminaSampleSheet_metadata.json  
  16s-A01_S56_L001_R1_001_fastqc_metadata.json  
  16s-A01_S56_L001_R2_001_fastqc_metadata.json  
  ...  
History/  
  History_E03.json
```

JSON Output Schema

Every JSON output file conforms to the common top-level schema with five universal fields:

```
{  
  "file_name":      "...",  
  "file_path":     "...",  
  "file_description": "...",  
  "instrument_type": "...",  
  "phase_workflow": "...",  
  "metadata": { ... },  
  "samples": [ ... ]  
}
```

The `metadata` block contains module-specific fields that vary by instrument. The `samples` list contains per-sample records where applicable. The five top-level fields are consistent across all extractor modules and aligned with the DECOS institutional Common Data Model.

A.6 Troubleshooting

Table A.2 lists common issues encountered during pipeline operation and their solutions.

Table A.2 *Common issues and solutions.*

Category	Issue	Solution
Installation	ModuleNotFoundError	Ensure all dependencies are installed: <code>pip install -r requirements.txt</code> . Verify the virtual environment is activated.
	Python version mismatch	The pipeline requires Python 3.9 or higher. Run <code>python3 --version</code> to verify.
Detection & Extraction	File not recognised	The file format is not yet supported by any extractor module. The pipeline logs a warning and continues. Check the terminal output for the skipped filename.
	Empty output directory	Verify that the input directory contains files in supported formats. Run a single known file first to confirm the pipeline is operational.
Output Quality	NaN values in JSON	Fields absent from the source file are preserved as-is. This is a known limitation. Null normalisation is planned for a future release.
	Incorrect field names	Verify you are using the latest version of the pipeline. Run <code>git pull origin main</code> to update.
RO-Crate	Descriptor shows version 1.1	Ensure <code>Crate_Generator.py</code> includes the post-processing step that enforces <code>@context</code> and <code>conformsTo</code> to version 1.2. See Section 3.6 of this thesis.

A.7 Version Control Strategy

This section describes the version control practices adopted for the pipeline repository and provides step-by-step guidelines for adding support for new instruments or file formats.

The pipeline source code is hosted on GitHub under the organisation account of the Research and Technology Institute (RIT) at Area Science Park:

https://github.com/RitAreaSciencePark/LAGE_Metadata_Extraction

Branching Model

The repository follows a simplified Git branching model suitable for a small development team:

- **main** branch: contains the stable, validated version of the pipeline. All code on this branch has been tested against the three case study datasets (ORID0087, ORID0085, ORID0036) with zero misclassifications.

Commit Conventions

Commit messages follow a descriptive format indicating the scope of the change:

```
[module] Short description of the change

Examples:
[Extractor_Nanopore] Fix pore_scan header detection
[Main_Auto_Processor] Add fallback logging for .pod5 files
[Crate_Generator] Enforce RO-Crate 1.2 conformsTo
[docs] Update README with TapeStation extractor details
[benchmark] Add processing time measurement script
```

The prefix in square brackets identifies which component is affected, making the Git history searchable by module.

Release Tagging

Stable releases are tagged using semantic versioning:

```
git tag -a v1.0.0 -m "Initial validated release"
git push origin v1.0.0
```

Version numbers follow the MAJOR.MINOR.PATCH convention:

- **MAJOR**: breaking changes to the JSON output schema or command-line interface,
- **MINOR**: new extractor modules or new features (backward-compatible),
- **PATCH**: bug fixes and documentation updates.

Licence and Attribution

The repository includes a LICENSE file (MIT) and a CITATION.cff file following the Citation File Format standard, enabling proper academic attribution when the pipeline is reused or referenced.

A.8 Guidelines for Adding New Extractors

The pipeline is designed for extensibility. Adding support for a new instrument or file format requires three steps, none of which modify existing code.

Step 1: Create the Extractor Module

Create a new Python file in the `Src/` directory. The filename should follow the established convention:

```
Src/Extractor_MyInstrument.py
```

The module must implement two functions:

- `is_my_instrument(file_path)` – a content-based validation function that returns `True` if the file matches the expected format, `False` otherwise.
- `one_single_file(root_dir, output_dir, file_name)` – the extraction function that parses the file and returns a list of structured metadata dictionaries.

Step 2: Implement Content-Based Validation

The validation function must inspect file content rather than relying on filename or extension. The following template illustrates the pattern:

```
def is_my_instrument(file_path):  
    """  
    Content-based validation for MyInstrument files.  
    Returns True if the file matches the expected format.  
    """  
    try:  
        with open(file_path, 'r', encoding='utf-8') as f:  
            first_lines = [f.readline() for _ in range(10)]  
  
        # Check for instrument-specific signatures  
        header_text = ''.join(first_lines)  
        if 'MyInstrument_Signature' in header_text:  
            return True  
        return False  
    except Exception:  
        return False
```

Important considerations for the validation function:

- Always wrap file reading in a `try/except` block. Binary files and encoding mismatches must not crash the pipeline.
- Read only the first few lines. Do not load the entire file into memory during validation.
- Check for content signatures (specific headers, keywords, column names) rather than file extensions.
- Return `False` for any ambiguous case. False negatives (skipping a valid file) are preferable to false positives (misclassifying a file).

Step 3: Implement the Extraction Function

The extraction function must conform to the common top-level JSON schema. The following template illustrates the required output structure:

```
def one_single_file(root_dir, output_dir, file_name):
    """
    Extract metadata from a MyInstrument file.
    Returns a list of metadata dictionaries.
    """
    file_path = os.path.join(root_dir, file_name)

    # Parse the file content
    # ... (instrument-specific parsing logic)

    metadata_record = {
        "file_name": file_name,
        "file_path": file_path,
        "file_description": "Description of this file type",
        "instrument_type": "MyInstrument_Model",
        "phase_workflow": "sequencing",
        "metadata": {
            # Module-specific fields
        },
        "samples": [
            # Per-sample records (if applicable)
        ]
    }

    # Write JSON output
    output_path = os.path.join(
        output_dir,
        file_name.replace('.csv', '_metadata.json')
    )
    with open(output_path, 'w', encoding='utf-8') as f:
        json.dump(metadata_record, f, indent=2)

    return [metadata_record]
```

The five common top-level fields must be present in every output:

- `file_name`: basename of the input file,
- `file_path`: full path at extraction time,
- `file_description`: human-readable description of the file role,
- `instrument_type`: canonical instrument name (e.g., `MyInstrument_Model`),

- `phase_workflow`: one of `sample_reception`, `pre_sequencing_qc`, `sequencing...`

Step 4: Register the Module

Open `Main_Auto_Processor.py` and add two lines:

```
import Extractor_MyInstrument

EXTRACTORS = [
    ...
    (Extractor_MyInstrument, "is_my_instrument"),
]
```

No other files need to be modified. The central engine will automatically include the new module in its validation polling sequence.

Step 5: Validate

After registration, run the pipeline on a known input file to verify correct detection and extraction:

```
python3 ./Src/Main_Auto_Processor.py ./Input/test_my_instrument_file.csv
↪ ./Output/Test_MyInstrument
```

Confirm that:

- The file is correctly detected (not skipped);
- The output JSON contains all five common top-level fields;
- The `instrument_type` value matches the canonical name;
- No existing extractors are affected (run the full benchmark suite on all three case study datasets to verify zero regressions).

A.9 Summary of Extensibility Mechanism

Adding support for a new instrument requires the following steps:

1. Create a new extractor module, for example: `Src/Extractor_MyInstrument.py`.
2. Implement a validation function, `is_my_instrument(file_path) -> bool`, that identifies compatible files based on their content rather than their filename.
3. Implement the extraction function, `one_single_file(root, out, name) -> list`, ensuring that all five common metadata fields are extracted and returned.

4. Register the extractor by importing the module and adding its entry to the **EXTRACTORS** registry in `Main_Auto_Processor.py`.
5. Verify the implementation by testing it on representative files, validating the generated output, and executing the full regression benchmark across all three datasets.

This mechanism ensures that the pipeline can grow to support new instruments without modifying any existing code, preserving backward compatibility and minimising regression risk.

References

- [1] Soraya Goodwin, John D McPherson, and W Richard McCombie. “Coming of age: ten years of next-generation sequencing technologies”. In: *Nature Reviews Genetics* 17 (2016), pp. 333–351. DOI: [10.1038/nrg.2016.49](https://doi.org/10.1038/nrg.2016.49) (cit. on pp. 1, 3, 4).
- [2] Frederick Sanger, Steven Nicklen, and Alan R Coulson. “DNA sequencing with chain-terminating inhibitors”. In: *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 74.12 (1977), pp. 5463–5467. DOI: [10.1073/pnas.74.12.5463](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.74.12.5463) (cit. on pp. 1, 3).
- [3] Jay Shendure and Hanlee Ji. “Next-generation DNA sequencing”. In: *Nature Biotechnology* 26.10 (2008), pp. 1135–1145. DOI: [10.1038/nbt1486](https://doi.org/10.1038/nbt1486). URL: <https://www.nature.com/articles/nbt1486> (cit. on pp. 1, 4).
- [4] Zachary D Stephens et al. “Big Data: Astronomical or Genomical?” In: *PLOS Biology* 13.7 (2015), e1002195. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pbio.1002195](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.1002195) (cit. on p. 1).
- [5] Mark D Wilkinson et al. “The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship”. In: *Scientific Data* 3 (2016), p. 160018. DOI: [10.1038/sdata.2016.18](https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18) (cit. on pp. 1, 12).
- [6] Stian Soiland-Reyes et al. “Packaging research artefacts with RO-Crate”. In: *Data Science* 5.2 (2022), pp. 97–138. DOI: [10.3233/DS-210053](https://doi.org/10.3233/DS-210053) (cit. on pp. 2, 14).
- [7] Alison Emm. *Genomic sequencing: A decade to a day*. Accessed: April 2026. Genomics Education Programme, Health Education England, June 2023. URL: <https://www.genomicseducation.hee.nhs.uk/blog/genomic-sequencing-a-decade-to-a-day/> (cit. on p. 3).
- [8] YourGenome.org. *Timeline: the past, present and future of DNA sequencing technologies*. Accessed: April 2026. 2020. URL: <https://www.yourgenome.org/theme/timeline-the-past-present-and-future-of-sequencing-technologies/> (cit. on p. 4).
- [9] Oxford Nanopore Technologies. *How Oxford Nanopore sequencing works*. Accessed: April 2026. 2026. URL: <https://nanoporetech.com/platform/technology> (cit. on p. 4).
- [10] MINSEQE Working Group. *Minimum Information about a high-throughput SEQuencing Experiment*. <https://www.fged.org/projects/minseqe/>. 2012 (cit. on pp. 6, 14).
- [11] Simon Andrews. *FastQC: a quality control tool for high throughput sequence data*. <https://www.bioinformatics.babraham.ac.uk/projects/fastqc/>. 2010 (cit. on p. 7).
- [12] Area Science Park. *LAGE – Genomics and Epigenomics Laboratory*. Accessed: April 2026. 2026. URL: <https://www.areasciencepark.it/en/research-infrastructures/life-sciences/lage-genomics-and-epigenomics-laboratory/> (cit. on p. 8).
- [13] *NovaSeq 6000 System Guide*. Accessed: April 2026. Illumina Inc. 2023. URL: https://support.illumina.com/sequencing/sequencing_instruments/novaseq-6000.html (cit. on pp. 8, 9).
- [14] CD Genomics. *NovaSeq 6000*. Accessed May 4, 2026. Sequencing service provider specifications. 2026. URL: <https://www.cd-genomics.com/novaseq-6000.html> (visited on 05/04/2026) (cit. on p. 8).

- [15] *bcl2fastq Conversion User Guide Version 1.8.4*. 15038058 Rev B. Official documentation: "BCL files contain base calls and quality scores... converted to FASTQ using bcl2fastq". Illumina Inc. Mar. 2013. URL: https://support.illumina.com/content/dam/illumina-support/documents/documentation/software_documentation/bcl2fastq/bcl2fastq_letterbooklet_15038058brpmi.pdf (visited on 05/04/2026) (cit. on p. 8).
- [16] Imperial Genomics Facility. *IGF Pipeline Help: Demultiplexing*. NovaSeq 6000 software versions: BCLConvert v4.4.6 (Apr 2026), bcl2fastq v2.20. 2026. URL: <https://imperial-genomics-facility.github.io/igf-pipeline-help/demultiplexing.html> (visited on 05/04/2026) (cit. on p. 8).
- [17] Oxford Nanopore Technologies. *How Oxford Nanopore sequencing works*. Accessed: April 2026. 2026. URL: <https://nanoporetech.com/platform/technology> (cit. on p. 9).
- [18] *PromethION Documentation*. Accessed: April 2026. Oxford Nanopore Technologies. 2023. URL: <https://nanoporetech.com/products/sequence/promethion/promethion-24> (cit. on p. 9).
- [19] *iScan System Documentation*. Accessed: April 2026. Illumina Inc. 2023. URL: <https://support.illumina.com> (cit. on p. 9).
- [20] CCPM University of Colorado Anschutz Medical Campus. *High-Throughput Genotyping: Illumina iScan*. Accessed: April 2026. University of Colorado Anschutz Medical Campus, CCPM, 2023. URL: <https://medschool.cuanschutz.edu/ccpm/cargo/high-throughput-genotyping/illumina-iscan> (cit. on p. 10).
- [21] EOSC Association. *EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda*. <https://www.eosc.eu>. 2021 (cit. on p. 12).
- [22] Pelin Yilmaz et al. "Minimum information about a marker gene sequence (MIMARKS) and minimum information about any (x) sequence (MIxS) specifications". In: *Nature Biotechnology* 29 (2011), pp. 415–420. DOI: [10.1038/nbt.1823](https://doi.org/10.1038/nbt.1823) (cit. on p. 14).
- [23] Philippe Rocca-Serra et al. "ISA software suite: supporting standards-compliant experimental annotation and enabling curation at the community level". In: *Bioinformatics* 26.18 (2010), pp. 2354–2356. DOI: [10.1093/bioinformatics/btq415](https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btq415) (cit. on p. 14).
- [24] Manu Sporny et al. *JSON-LD 1.1: A JSON-based Serialization for Linked Data*. W3C Recommendation, <https://www.w3.org/TR/json-ld11/>. 2020 (cit. on p. 14).
- [25] Ramanathan V Guha, Dan Brickley, and Steve Macbeth. "Schema.org: evolution of structured data on the web". In: *Communications of the ACM* 59.2 (2016), pp. 44–51. DOI: [10.1145/2844544](https://doi.org/10.1145/2844544) (cit. on p. 15).
- [26] Tim Berners-Lee. *Linked Data - Design Issues*. Accessed: April 2026. W3C, July 2006. URL: <https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html> (cit. on p. 15).
- [27] Douglas Lowe Stian Soiland-Reyes Stuart Owen. *Packaging Data with RO-Crate: HTML Preview*. https://www.researchobject.org/packaging_data_with_ro-crate/12-html-preview.html. Accessed: April 2026. Research Object Community, 2026 (cit. on p. 63).